

TERRA VISION

Integrated Earth Observation Based Platform, for Novel Services
to Enhance the Mining Life Cycle of Critical Raw Materials

D4.4

TERRAVISION technical specifications and system architecture
design

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
ARD	Analysis Ready Data
BSQ	Band Sequential (a format for hyperspectral data)
CARD4L	Common Architecture for Remote Sensing Data
CDSE	Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
CoAP	Constrained Application Protocol
CSR	Corporate Sustainability Reporting
CWL	Common Workflow Language
DBSCAN	Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise
DInSAR	Differential Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar
DSM	Digital Surface Model
DTM	Digital Terrain Model
ECW	Enhanced Compression Wavelet
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
EnMap	Environmental Mapping and Analysis Program
EO	Earth Observation

ETL	Extract, Transform, Load
GeoJSON	Geographic JavaScript Object Notation
GeoTIFF	Geographic Tagged Image File Forma
GEP	Platform
GIS	Geographic Information System
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GRASS	Geographic Resources Analysis Support System
HDR	Header file
HR	High Resolution
IFG	Interferometric
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
IoT	Internet of Things
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JWT	JSON Web Token
KML	Keyhole Markup Language
LAS	Lidar data format (LASer)
LLaVA	Large Language and Vision Assistant
LST	Land Surface Temperature
LiDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
LoRaWAN	Long Range Wide Area Network
LoS	Line-of-Sight
ML	Machine Learning

MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
MSW	Mock Service Worker
NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index
NDWI	Normalized Difference Water Index
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OPK	Omega (roll), Phi (pitch), and Kappa (yaw)
PgSTAC	PostgreSQL SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog
PRISMA	PRecursore IperSpettrale della Missione Applicativa (an Italian hyperspectral satellite mission)
PSI	Persistent Scatterers Interferometry
PyWPS	Python Web Processing Service
RBAC	Role-Based Access Control
REST	REpresentational State Transfer
RM	Raw Material
RNN	Recurrent Neural Networks
ROI	Regions of Interest
SAM (Segment)	Segment Anything Model
SAM (Spectral)	Spectral Angle Mapper
SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
SI	Sustainability Index
SLC	Single Look Complex

SLSTR	Sea and Land Surface Temperature Radiometer
SR	Super-Resolution
STAC	SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog
SVM	Support Vector Machine
TFW	TIFF World File
TIR	Thermal Infrared
UDP	User Defined Processes
UI	User Interface
UTM	Universal Transverse Mercator
UX	User Experience
UNFC	United Nations Framework Classification
VHR	Very High Resolution
VML	Vision Model Large
WCS	Web Coverage Service
WFS	Web Feature Service
WGS84	World Geodetic System 1984
WMS	Web Map Service
WMTS	Web Map Tile Service
WP	Work Package
XRF	X-ray Fluorescence

H1 – EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable specifies the system requirements and architecture for Earth Observation (EO) data mining services. It describes the TERRAVISION architecture, including system layers, components, the connectivity with the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem (CDSE) and provides information about the functional blocks.

H2 – GOAL/OBJECTIVES

This document defines the specifications and system architecture for building EO data mining services. It focuses on performance, scalability, security and privacy while defining both functional and non-functional criteria to enable use-case-based, user-centric EO services. It also introduces the TERRAVISION reference architecture, which describes the many system layers, parts and integration points required to ensure seamless communication between EO services and the ecosystem as a whole. In addition, the document breaks down the system modules into functional blocks, assigning technologies to certain capabilities and providing critical information for the construction of the tooling framework in the work that follows.

H3 – METHODOLOGY

The TERRAVISION platform's high-level architecture was established by defining the key elements and interactions of the individual building blocks and services. This led to the creation of a visual representation of the system, which provides a detailed overview of its components, levels and interactions. The architectural views of the functional components were subsequently finalized. To facilitate the capture of detailed information for each building block, a standardized "TERRAVISION Architecture View Template" was developed. This ensured consistency with the overall architecture. The template was completed by the relevant teams, which enabled the finalization of detailed descriptions of each component and the solidification of the architectural framework. At the same time, a preliminary framework for the platform's application was established. The requirements and specifications for the app's User Experience (UX) design were defined, and the core components were developed concurrently. The data flows for TERRAVISION services were finalized as part of the process.

H4 – OUTCOMES/CONCLUSIONS

The architecture ensures the efficient construction of the TERRAVISION platform. The architecture provides the environment for key elements to be integrated into the platform, ensuring alignment with the project objectives. It serves as a guide for task leaders who want to develop and implement the various project mining services. This outcome resulted from ongoing collaboration with task leaders, addressing early design challenges as they arose. The architecture is designed to be flexible, allowing for future improvements.

Key outcomes/conclusions in bullet points

- Comprehensive Architecture Diagram: A high-level architecture diagram illustrating the major components and their interactions.
- Detailed Component Descriptions: Clarify the roles and functions of each system element.
- Optimized Design: Feedback has refined the high-level architecture to meet project requirements and accurately reflect the system.
- Foundation for Future Development: The architecture supports Task 7.1 and lays the groundwork for future phases.

1. Introduction

The document constitutes the initial reference for the development and implementation of the TERRAVISION Platform. It lists the functional properties needed to develop end-user and use case-driven EO mining services, as identified in Tasks 4.1 and 4.2. It also addresses non-functional requirements related to performance, scalability, security, and privacy. The system-level specification provides the high-level view of the layers and components, as well as tools and applications, specifying their interaction patterns the technical integration points, the interconnection scheme, and the specific interfaces for the exchange of information among them, but also with the CDSE. The core system functionalities identified through the requirements analysis are assigned to specific system components and aligned with relevant technological areas. Each module is further decomposed into high-level functional blocks (to be used as the basis for the subsequent detailed specification of each component) and supported primitives and interfaces.

1.1 Purpose of the Deliverable

The objectives related to this deliverable have been achieved in full and as scheduled.

1.2 Intended Audience

The intended audience for this deliverable includes the leaders of the tasks whose outputs define the functional characteristics of the platform. In particular, it is addressed to VITO, DIMAP, SINTEF, AUTH, AURORA, CORE, GEOS, ICCS and ITA, who have specific tasks to complete and are included in the following Work Packages (WPs): WP4 - Requirements, Specifications and Overall Architecture, WP5/6 - Data Ecosystem for Large scale EO mining services, WP7/8 – Analysis Ready Data (ARD) and Raw spectral signatures, WP9/10 - EO services for the mining industry, WP11 - Green & Resilience Accountability component. This deliverable ensures that the above participants have a clear understanding of the system specifications, architecture and their roles in terms of their contribution to the overall project objectives.

1.3 Deliverable structure and relation with other work packages/deliverables

This deliverable starts with an executive summary, which states the Grant Agreement on which the methodology was based in order to meet the specific requirements of TERRAVISION. The section "Goals/Objectives" describes the main purpose of the document which is to define the platform architecture based on the requirements for EO mining services, covering both functional and non-functional requirements. The "Methodology" section describes the steps taken to create the architecture, while the "Outcomes/Conclusions" section summarises the main achievements in the architectural design.

The Introduction gives a summary of the deliverable, covering the high-level specifications, essential functionalities, and major aspects required for the development and integration of the TERRAVISION Platform. Following the introduction, Section 1.1 (Purpose of the Deliverable) confirms that the objectives of this deliverable have been fully met as specified. Section 1.2 (Intended Audience) identifies the key stakeholders to ensure that they have a clear understanding of their roles and contributions. This section 2 outlines the architecture of the TERRAVISION platform, starting with its conceptual topology in Section 2.1, which integrates different data sources, including EO, airborne and in-situ data to improve resource management (RM). Section 2.2 details the methodology used to develop the architecture, focusing on the use of 'views' and 'perspectives' for clarity. Section 2.3 discusses architectural goals and constraints, emphasising scalability, modularity and interoperability. Section 2.4 provides an overall architectural view showing how the platform harmonises data for advanced EO mining services, with subsections covering system functionality, data management and deployment.

Section 3 covers the system's functions including but not limited to the inputs/outputs of each building block while section 4 explains how data are managed and flow. Section 5 addresses the practical aspects of deployment and operations. Section 6 of the document refers to the architectural perspectives, which are divided into two subsections: "Security and Privacy Perspective" and "Performance & Scalability Perspective."

The deliverable is connected to numerous other work packages in the TERRAVISION project. It is a critical component of WP4 (Requirements, Specifications, and Overall Architecture), which includes the system requirements and architecture required to drive the development of EO mining services. It is developed based on the functional and non-functional requirements derived by Tasks 4.1 and 4.2. Furthermore, this deliverable is aligned with WP5/6 (Data Ecosystem for Large Scale EO Mining Services), WP7/8 (ARD and Raw Spectral Signatures), WP9/10 (EO Services for the Mining Industry), and WP11 (Green & Resilience Accountability Component).

2. System Architecture of TERRAVISION

This chapter begins by describing the TERRAVISION Suite's conceptual topology, which provides a foundation for comprehending the system's general structure and key components. It then describes the approach used to define the architecture, as well as the system's methodical development process. The following key sections are included: Architectural Goals and Constraints, which describe the objectives and limitations that guide the system's design; and Architectural Topology, which examines the high-level layout of system components and their interactions. The Overall Architectural View offers an integrated perspective of these elements, while the Functional View focuses on the specific functionalities of various modules and their contributions to the system's goals. It highlights various use cases and applications, demonstrating how TERRAVISION supports both regional and local mineral exploration, monitoring and forecasting surface motion, stockpile volume monitoring, primary and secondary raw material mapping and dynamic hazard mapping through advanced data integration, processing, and analysis methods. This comprehensive overview provides a clear and detailed roadmap of TERRAVISION's architecture and functionality.

2.1 TERRAVISION Suite Conceptual Topology

TERRAVISION is developing a cutting-edge platform to optimize mining operations through the utilization of a range of data sources, including EO, aerial, and on-site data. This platform unifies these data types into a unified system, thereby enhancing the monitoring and management of Raw Materials (RM). It utilizes multi-sensor data fusion techniques to optimize the deployment of EO technologies for critical RM and the full range of mining phases. The system has been designed to integrate seamlessly with existing industry practices, overcoming limitations in data resolution and providing real-time updates on material supply, ground movements and potential risks. TERRAVISION will enable mining to become more efficient, resilient and sustainable.

Figure 1. Innovation pillars and services of TERRAVISION EO Mining Platform

2.2 Methodology of architecture definition

The development of the TERRAVISION toolbox system architecture relies on well-established definitions and methods for architectural design based on (Woods, 2005) and Ogush, Coleman, and Beringer (2000). This methodology advocates for the use of 'views' and 'perspectives' to offer a clear and thorough depiction of the system's components and their functions. Additionally, the system architecture is derived from TERRAVISION's user scenarios, system specifications, and the operational processes of the funding agencies. A widely recognized method involves breaking down the architectural description into distinct views, with each view addressing a specific aspect of the system. Below is a formal definition of an architectural view:

"A view is a representation of one or more structural aspects of an architecture that illustrates how the architecture addresses one or more concerns held by one or more of its stakeholders" Nick Rozanski (2005). Software Systems Architecture: Working with Stakeholders Using Viewpoints and Perspectives.

The current architecture document will consider the following views:

Functional View: This outlines the system's functional components of the system, detailing their functions and interfaces.

Information View: This defines the static structure of information and illustrates dynamic data flows, explaining how information is *"defined, structured, stored, processed, managed, and exchanged"* Magerkurth (2012). IoT-A Deliverable D1.4 Converged architectural reference model for the IoT v2.0. IoT-A Consortium.

Deployment & Operation View: This focuses on installation, hardware integration with existing infrastructure, and maintenance, while also suggesting technologies for system deployment.

Perspectives are also essential in characterizing non-functional aspects of the system, which are often referred to as "ilities. *"One may locate a formal definition in Rozanski (2005): "An architectural perspective is a collection of activities, checklists, tactics and guidelines to guide the process of ensuring that a system exhibits a particular set of closely related quality properties that require consideration across a number of the system's architectural views"*.

The following perspectives will be taken into consideration while creating the architectural concept:

- Security covers the security aspects of the TERRAVISION system architecture, including access control, authentication, authorization, and data integrity and confidentiality.
- Performance and Scalability: addresses trade-offs between scalability concerns and enhanced system component performance.

2.3 Architectural Goals and Constraints

The TERRAVISION platform has been designed to integrate a variety of tools in order to effectively manage inputs and outputs by converting them into a standardized format. This central architecture provides a unified system that supports all partners, ensuring that all components

work together seamlessly. The platform is designed to ensure high performance, scalability, and robust security, while also prioritizing interoperability. By standardizing data and centralizing processing, TERRAVISION enables smooth teamwork and consistent management of information among all partners, which boosts the system's overall efficiency and effectiveness. More specifically:

- **Scalability, Modularity, and Future-Proofing**

Terravision's architecture is built to handle growth and change, ensuring it can scale smoothly as data volumes increase and new datasets from evolving EO platforms or updated in-situ sensors come online. Its modular design allows each part of the system to function independently while still working seamlessly with the rest, making it easy to add new services or features, such as future EO services or mining-related tools, without disrupting the current setup. The platform also uses cloud-based processing and distributed data storage, enabling it to manage larger data loads while keeping performance steady as the number of users and datasets grows. Beyond that, it's flexible enough to accommodate new technologies like advanced Machine Learning (ML) models and analytics, as well as future mining services. This adaptability ensures Terravision remains valuable and up-to-date as both mining technology and EO data continue to evolve.

- **Multi-Source Data Integration**

The architecture is designed to seamlessly integrate data from multiple sources such as EO data, in-situ sensors, aerial imagery, and ground-based measurements into a complete system. This integration allows users to utilize a wide range of data for the different applications. For example, it supports raw material exploration by combining data from multispectral, hyperspectral, and geophysical sources to help identify deposits at both regional and local scales. It also facilitates the continuous monitoring of extraction rates and stockpile volumes in open-pit mines by incorporating data from optical and SAR sensors. Additionally, the system enables near real-time risk assessments by generating dynamic hazard maps to monitor potential threats, such as ground deformation or environmental hazards.

- **Performance, Security, and Interoperability**

The TERRAVISION architecture is designed to prioritize performance, security, and interoperability to ensure smooth and secure operations. It is optimized to handle large datasets and real-time analytics, using advanced data pipelines and high-performance computing to deliver fast processing and reliable service. Security is a core focus, with robust protocols in place such as data encryption, authentication methods, and GDPR compliance, ensuring that sensitive information remains protected throughout the mining process. Additionally, TERRAVISION follows open standards like those from the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) and ISO, which ensures compatibility with external systems and platforms, including the CDSE. This commitment to interoperability facilitates the easy exchange of information between TERRAVISION and other mining or EO systems.

- **Boosting Team Collaboration and System Efficiency**

The architecture fosters smooth teamwork and collaboration by providing a centralized platform where data, insights, and services are easily accessible to all project partners. By

streamlining data flows and standardizing processes, the platform ensures efficient management of raw materials data, enhancing the overall productivity of the TERRAVISION partners.

2.4 Overall Architectural View

Figure 2 illustrates a mineral exploration platform that uses a variety of data sources, including EO satellites, ground sensors, and field samples. The data are processed to ensure consistency, harmonized, and then analysed with ML techniques to provide useful insights. The platform provides EO mining services on CDSE, Geohazards Exploitation Platform (GEP), and TerraFusion Platform, addressing the various stages of the mining lifecycle. In summary, this platform provides a comprehensive approach to mineral exploration, integrating remote sensing, field data and advanced analytics to facilitate informed decision-making.

Figure 2. Diagram of the overall architectural view

3. System Architecture Functional View

The functional view of a system decomposes it into individual building blocks, focusing on their specific roles, services and interfaces. It defines the architecture of the system by outlining the key functional elements, their responsibilities, and their supported interfaces. This view provides a clear understanding of the structure of the system, documenting how the different components work together to deliver the overall functionality. It is primarily concerned with the behaviour of the system and how its parts work together to achieve the system's objectives.

3.1 Data Inputs

This section covers components responsible for data acquisition and initial collection from various sources.

3.1.1 OpenEO on CDSE

Description

openEO represents an innovative community standard that revolutionizes geospatial data processing and analysis. This groundbreaking framework provides a novel approach to accessing, processing, and analysing diverse EO data. By adopting openEO, developers, researchers, and data scientists gain access to a unified and interoperable platform, empowering them to harness distributed computing environments and leverage cloud-based resources for addressing complex geospatial challenges.

With openEO's collaborative nature, users can seamlessly share code, workflows, and data processing methods across platforms and tools, fostering collaboration and advancing the accessibility, scalability, and reproducibility of EO data. Additionally, openEO provides intuitive programming libraries that enable easy analysis of diverse EO datasets. These libraries facilitate efficient access and processing of large-scale data across multiple infrastructures, supporting various applications, including exploratory research, detailed mapping, and information extraction from EO. Moreover, this streamlined approach enhances the development process, enabling the utilization of EO data for a wide range of applications and services.

In the TERRAVISION project, we aim to integrate the openEO instance hosted on the CDSE. This federated instance provides access to cloud processing resources and hosts one of the largest collections of datasets from multiple openEO providers, including the full Sentinel-2 archive. More information on this concept is

	<p>available at https://documentation.dataspace.copernicus.eu/APIs/openEO/federation/openeo_federation.html.</p> <p>Using the openEO client libraries, the CDSE federated instance will be utilized to build processing workflows by combining different data sources and processing them in a scalable cloud environment. Additionally, reusable building blocks will be created using the concept of openEO's User Defined Processes (UDPs, https://openeo.github.io/openeo-python-client/udp.html), encapsulating complete processing workflows in single processes that can be integrated into other workflows or executed on demand. These openEO UDPs can also be published on the CDSE Algorithm Plaza (https://marketplace-portal.dataspace.copernicus.eu/) to make them available to a larger community and foster the reuse of the services built within TERRAVISION.</p>
<p>Building blocks</p>	<p>CDSE openEO Federation (https://documentation.dataspace.copernicus.eu/APIs/openEO/federation/openeo_federation.html)</p> <p>OpenEO backend that provides access to scalable cloud processing resources and EO datasets.</p> <p>OpenEO client tools and libraries (https://documentation.dataspace.copernicus.eu/APIs/openEO/openeo.html, https://openeo.org/documentation/1.0/#introduction)</p> <p>Development tools to create openEO workflows.</p> <p>All the above building blocks are already available and will be utilized to develop the services in the TERRAVISION project.</p>
<p>Interfaces</p>	<p>The integration is based on the usage of the openEO API. More information on this Application Programming Interface (API) is available on the following pages:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://openeo.org/ • https://dataspace.copernicus.eu/analyse/apis/openeo-api <p>An overview of all the supported file formats is available at https://openeofed.dataspace.copernicus.eu/openeo/file_formats</p>

Figure 3. Functional view of CDSE openEO integration

3.1.2 Airborne Data Collection and Pre-processing

<p>Description</p>	<p>The workflow for airborne data collection and pre-processing involves a collection of various data sets over the different demonstrators and mining sites with a range of sensor of Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR), image, hyperspectral and thermal platforms, and setups integrate seamlessly datasets produced into the TERRAVISION ecosystem.</p> <p>Data collection steps including metadata protocols, will be modified to be direct integration into the TerraFusion Platform. Once all sensors of data are processed, it will be integrated into an open workflow model to have direct integration into the TERRAVISION EO Mining platform. Data interfaces will be optimized for online and near online integration of the data collection into the overall TERRAVISION EO Mining platform.</p>
<p>Building blocks</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EO-Data Trajectories Processing for the trajectories of all sensors.

- **LiDAR**
To generate Digital Terrain Model (DTM), Digital Surface Model (DSM) and contour that also usable for the other sensor processing.
- **Camera Images**
To get a scheme for check point for Thermal and Hyperspectral.
- **Thermal**
Processing to get some ground emissivity.
- **Hyperspectral**
Measurement of reflected solar radiation in many narrow contiguous spectral bands.

Interfaces The TERRAVISION airborne data collection and processed will utilize with Representational State Transfer (REST) APIs or with the usage of data streams to the TERRAVISION Platform. Outputs of the production are LiDAR dataset, digital terrain and surface models, contour datasets, orthophotos, thematic mineral, and hyperspectral data – all data coreference in Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) World Geodetic System 1984 (WGS84) as a local system.

Figure 4. Functional view of TERRAVISION Airborne Data Collection and Processing

3.1.2.1 EO-Data Trajectories

After data collection, trajectories EO data are downloaded from the Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS)/ Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) system. The processing against multiple GNSS base stations for precise trajectory. Kalman filter based processing of GNSS trajectory and INS data to precise XYZ OPK and time stamps.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION EO-Data Trajectories	The service will include the output of continuous trajectory in Keyhole Markup Language (KML) format. It is basically the flight lines of data collection where each of lines contain the references – coordinates, altitude, and rotation of data collection over three different mining companies. This can be used for marking of the events for images, thermal images, and every line of the hyperspectral scanner.

3.1.2.2 LiDAR

A LiDAR point cloud dataset is created when an area is laser scanned using LiDAR, or light detection and ranging. The dataset contains the X, Y and Z coordinate of every visible detail of the project site. A laser scanner captures point clouds with the highest accuracy. Point clouds provide powerful and dynamic information for a project. By representing spatial data as a collection of coordinates, point clouds deliver large datasets that can be mined for information. The visualization and analysis of point cloud data are invaluable for decision making.

LiDAR systems for mining industries can produce Geographic Information System (GIS) data for DSM and DTM models, to capture geospatial information of the natural surface, the infrastructure of a mine, its planned extension, and to calculate production volumes. It provides precise elevation data, inventory information, surface or volume calculations, accurate pit models, and contour maps in a fraction of the time.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION LiDAR	This service will provide classified LiDAR points cloud. The input for this dataset is in LASer (LAS) format. LiDAR point clouds can be very dense and contain billions of points, due to software limitation, LiDAR dataset will be provided in 1km X 1km tiles plan. For this project, the LiDAR provided height information for terrain and vegetation analysis based on 50-100 points per square meter. LiDAR points cloud is classified according to LAS point cloud classification scheme as table below:

Code	Description
1	Processed, but unclassified
2	Ground
4	Vegetation
7	Low noise
8	Model key points

From this LiDAR data, a model such as Digital Terrain Model (DTM) and Digital Surface Model (DSM) can be produced from it. DTM can be used for creation of contours, land-use studies, geological applications, and planetary science. It is created from code 2 – ground class of point cloud. In contrast DSM are preferred for visualization applications and it is created from all LiDAR point cloud except for code 7 – low noise class. The output for DTM and DSM is in TIFF file. Contour also will be generated from DTM with the output in shapefile format.

3.1.2.3 Camera Images

An aerial photograph that has been geometrically corrected follows a given map projection to produce an orthophoto image. Orthophoto will be used in GIS as a map accurate background image. This aerial photography has proven to be an important tool in support of mineral exploration projects. It provides geologists and field crews with the location of tracks, roads, fences, and inhabited areas. This is important for mapping out potential access corridors for exploration areas and considering the environmental impact of large projects. The orthophoto data is also useful for mapping outcrops and regulating systematics and vegetation cover across exploration blocks and over regional areas.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Camera Images	This service will provide orthophoto images in Enhanced Compression Wavelet (ECW) format. The camera provides images with a resolution of 4-6cm Airborne Complex Mine Survey. It can be used for basemap and plan drawing processes at various scales. It gives project managers an accurate look at the entire site, without gaps or distortions.

3.1.2.4 Thermal

Thermal remote sensing is a technique to measure radiation emitting from the ground object of any entity. The basis for the determination is the ratio of the degree of thermal radiation between temperature and wavelength. This thermal radiation is measured using a thermal sensor. Thermal

remote sensing can play a vital role in temperature and soil moisture monitoring and disaster prevention.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Thermal	<p>This service will provide an absolute calibrated temperature where produce from airborne data collection and relative temperature of thermal images that is calculated based on comparing the temperature of the grass from satellite images and the result from airborne thermal. Both output formats are in TIFF and TIFF World File (TFW) files. The spatial resolution for thermal dataset is 0.8-1 meter.</p> <p>Using thermal images, it is possible to track the temperature of tailings dams and look for hotspots that have unstable slopes and might be signs of imminent disaster. Thermal images can also be used to study the temperature of water bodies near mining sites and detect changes in temperature that could indicate pollution. Mining industries can use this data to reduce their environmental pollution and comply with regulations. Thermal images can come handy in estimating risks of landslides that take place due to open pit mining. It can measure the moisture in soil content which can also help in predicting the risk of land slide.</p>

3.1.2.5 *Hyperspectral*

Hyperspectral imaging collects and processes information from across the electromagnetic spectrum. The goal of hyperspectral imaging is to obtain the spectrum for each pixel in the image of a scene, with the purpose of identifying materials, or detecting processes.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Hyperspectral	<p>This service provides hyperspectral scanners covering the VNIR range 400 to 1000nm with 160 bands, 0.4-0.5m resolution and the SWIR range 1000 to 2500nm with 256 bands, 0.8-1m resolution. The hyperspectral data will be delivered in Band Sequential (BSQ) format, along with an accompanying Header (HDR) file.</p> <p>The hyperspectral data are processed to mineral maps using principal component analysis, local as well as free available spectral libraries of Spectral Angle Mapper (SAM) and Support Vector Machine (SVM) to mineral maps for the target minerals. The mineral maps are provided, combined with quality maps, and are ready for implementation into the mining package.</p>

The hyperspectral data are used over the mine area for several purposes including the analysis of the mine faces using the hyperspectral signatures.

Furthermore, the hyperspectral dataset provides a baseline for the mine operator on the status of the mine, to be used in the future for comparison purposes and in case of operational or environmental issues.

3.1.3 In-situ Sensors, Planning and Installation

Description

The goal is to develop a comprehensive framework to plan, install, and integrate in-situ sensors at mining sites, supporting large-scale EO mining services. The approach addresses the full lifecycle of sensor deployment, from planning to ongoing data management, ensuring optimal functionality and integration into a cloud-based platform.

Data is collected from in-situ sensors installed across mining sites on critical parameters such as ground deformation, water pressure, and environmental variables. Sensors stream data continuously, and periodic calibrations ensure data quality.

Sensor data is transmitted preferably wirelessly through established communication networks (e.g., LoRaWAN, Wi-Fi) to the TerraFusion Platform, ensuring a real-time data stream. Communication protocols ensure secure and stable data flow. To enable the seamless integration of in-situ sensors at mining sites with the larger EO data ecosystem, several technical components must be defined. This includes the design of databases to store and manage data, API requirements for efficient data exchange between systems, and other technical considerations like security, data processing, and scalability. The following provides a comprehensive breakdown of these critical elements:

Database Specifications

A robust and scalable database system is essential for storing the vast and varied data generated from in-situ sensors, aerial imagery, and EO data. The database must accommodate real-time data streams while ensuring data integrity, security, and accessibility for advanced analytics.

- **Database Type**

Depending on the type of data, different types of databases will be used. Relational databases such as PostgreSQL or MySQL will be used to store structured data such as sensor metadata, while time-series databases such as InfluxDB or TimescaleDB will be used for continuous real-time sensor data streams. NoSQL databases will be used to handle unstructured or semi-structured data such as images and logs, while spatial databases such as PostGIS (an extension of PostgreSQL) will manage geospatial data such as maps and GPS coordinates from EO systems.

- **Key Features**

The database will be designed with key features such as scalability, real-time data handling and high availability. It must be able to scale to accommodate growing datasets as more sensors are deployed and the frequency of sensor readings increases. It will support geospatial queries and operations, allowing efficient mapping of sensor locations and integration with satellite imagery. Data retention and archiving mechanisms will also be required to ensure that older data is securely stored and available for long-term analysis, while meeting regulatory requirements.

- **Database Schema**

A well-defined database schema will support the storage and organisation of data, including sensor metadata (e.g. sensor ID, location, calibration information), time series data and geospatial data from EO systems.

- **Data Quality Control**

Calibration data must be tracked for each sensor, documenting events and settings. Automated anomaly detection systems will be set up to identify problems such as abnormal sensor readings, missing data or malfunctions. Quality control flags will be attached to each data point to ensure that any irregularities are identified and addressed in real time.

API Requirements

APIs are critical for enabling communication between in-situ sensors, databases, the TerraFusion Platform, and external systems such as the CDSE. APIs must be well-designed to support interoperability, data exchange, and scalability.

- **API Types**

A RESTful API will be the primary interface. It will allow for the efficient querying and exchange of data between systems. This architecture is scalable and flexible and can accommodate diverse data formats like JSON and XML. In addition to RESTful APIs, WebSocket-based APIs will be used to support real-time

data transmission from sensors. This enables low-latency, bidirectional communication, which is essential for time-sensitive data streams.

- **Key API Endpoints**

Specific API endpoints will be defined for various functions. These will include endpoints for uploading real-time or batch sensor data (/sensor_data/upload), querying historical data (/sensor_data/query), retrieving sensor metadata (/metadata/sensor), and accessing geospatial information (/geospatial/query). Additional endpoints will trigger alerts in cases of anomaly detection (/alerts/anomalies), such as unusual data patterns or sensor malfunctions. An endpoint for checking the status of sensors (/status), including battery levels and connectivity, will be established to ensure operational efficiency.

- **API Security**

Security is a crucial aspect of the API design. Authentication via OAuth 2.0 will be implemented to ensure that only authorized users and systems have access to the data. Rate limiting will be used to prevent system overload by controlling the number of requests that can be made in a given timeframe. All data transmissions will be encrypted using HTTPS or TLS, ensuring that sensitive environmental and operational data is protected during communication.

- **Data Formats**

JSON/GeoJSON will be the format for sensor data and geospatial data exchange. CSV is to be used for bulk data download, as it is suitable for analytics and offline processing. Finally, binary streaming is the most efficient way to transfer continuous sensor streams or large imagery files.

Technical Considerations

The effective integration of in-situ sensors at mining sites into a comprehensive EO-based data ecosystem demands the development of a robust, scalable, and secure technical framework. It is essential that the database is capable of handling large volumes of heterogeneous data, while the application programming interfaces (APIs) must facilitate real-time, secure communication between systems. Technical considerations, including data quality control, cloud processing, security, and scalability, ensure that the system provides reliable, actionable insights for mining operations, thereby enhancing both safety and efficiency.

- **Data Interoperability**

The platform must support various data formats, such as time-series data, geospatial data, and images, while maintaining compatibility with industry standards like GeoJSON and netCDF. Algorithms and middleware will be developed to facilitate cross-system data fusion, allowing in-situ sensor data to be combined with satellite and aerial imagery for enhanced analysis. For example, ground deformation data collected from sensors can be overlaid with satellite-based deformation maps, providing a more comprehensive view of the mining site's condition.
- **Data Processing and Analytics**

The TERRAVISION platform will use cloud computing resources like AWS or Azure to perform real-time analytics, supporting functions such as geo-hazard detection and anomaly detection. The platform will integrate ML models to process real-time and historical datasets, enabling the prediction of future events such as slope instability based on sensor trends. In remote mining sites with limited connectivity, edge computing devices will be used to pre-process and filter data locally, reducing bandwidth usage and latency before transmitting essential data to the cloud.
- **Data Security and Compliance**

All data stored in the database will be encrypted both at rest and in transit. Role-based access control (RBAC) will be implemented to limit data access based on user roles, ensuring that only authorized personnel can access or modify sensitive information. Regular integrity checks will be conducted to ensure that data remains intact during transmission and storage. Compliance with regulations such as GDPR will be maintained, particularly in handling environmental and operational data that could be considered sensitive.
- **Scalability and Performance**

Central to the platform's ability to handle increasing data loads as more sensors are deployed. Cloud-native infrastructure, such as Kubernetes, will enable horizontal scaling, allowing the system to handle more data and users without performance degradation. Caching mechanisms will be implemented for frequently accessed data, such as historical sensor readings or metadata, improving response times for common queries. Load balancing will distribute API requests across multiple servers, ensuring high availability and performance during peak usage.
- **Maintenance and Upgrades**

It is essential to guarantee that in-situ sensors are equipped with the capacity to receive remote firmware updates, including those intended to rectify errors, enhance performance, or introduce

new features. This must be achieved without necessitating physical access. Furthermore, a monitoring system, such as Prometheus or Grafana, should be implemented to track the health of the sensors, the quality of data transmission, and the overall system load. This system should be designed to automatically generate alerts in the event of issues, such as sensor failure or data transmission delays.

Building blocks

- **Mining Operations and Process Analysis**
A thorough understanding of mining operations is essential for selecting in-situ sensors to monitor critical parameters. This involves site assessments to identify the appropriate sensor types and placements.
- **Sensor Installation Plan**
A plan will detail sensor deployment, including optimal placement, power supply options, and communication networks. It will ensure reliable data transmission to the cloud while optimizing power for continuous operation in remote environments.
- **Collaboration with Site Personnel**
Engagement with mining site personnel will be essential for the smooth installation and ongoing maintenance of the sensors. Training programs will be developed to ensure that local staff are familiar with sensor maintenance, calibration, and troubleshooting procedures. This collaboration will also ensure that sensors are installed and integrated into existing site workflows without disrupting operations.
- **Data Quality Control and Calibration**
Calibration routines and quality control protocols will ensure sensor data accuracy and reliability, including automated anomaly detection and alarms for quick intervention.
- **Communication Protocols for Data Transmission**
Secure communication channels will transmit data from in-situ sensors to the TerraFusion Platform, using LoRaWAN, Wi-Fi, or satellite, tailored to site needs. Backup systems will ensure continuous data transmission during outages.
- **Ongoing Maintenance and Support**
A long-term maintenance protocol will ensure sensor functionality through routine inspections, remote diagnostics, and software updates. A schedule will minimize downtime and keep sensors operational.
- **Data Integration and Cloud Management**
Data from in-situ sensors will be integrated into the TerraFusion Platform alongside aerial imagery and satellite data to enable

advanced analytics and informed decision-making in mining operations.

Interfaces

- **In-Situ Sensor Interface**

The interface is necessary for the continuous input of sensor data (e.g., water pressure, ground deformation) into the central system. Sensor data is collected in real time and then formatted for compatibility with EO and aerial datasets.
- **TERRAVISION Platform Integration**

An interface is required to facilitate the connection of in-situ sensor data to the TerraFusion Platform via secure protocols. The platform will oversee the management of both satellite and ground-based data, thereby facilitating dynamic visualisation and analytics. Data is stored and processed via a cloud-based architecture, which allows for scalability and integration with other EO systems, such as the CDSE.
- **Data Communications Networks**

The interface between sensors and the cloud enables wireless data transfer via LoRaWan, Wi-Fi, or satellite communications, thus ensuring a reliable data flow even in remote mining locations. Secure communication protocols are established for both real-time data transmission and backup storage in case of connection issues.
- **Control and Calibration Systems**

The calibration interface permits remote and on-site adjustment of sensor parameters, thereby ensuring ongoing accuracy. The platform incorporates quality control measures that identify and rectify data inconsistencies.

Figure 5. Functional view of In-situ sensors planning, installation and integration.

3.1.3.1 Mining Operations and Process Analysis

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
Mining Operations and Process Analysis	A thorough understanding of mining operations is necessary to determine the appropriate in-situ sensors required for monitoring. This begins with a site-specific assessment, identifying critical parameters to be monitored, such as ground deformation, water pressure, and environmental variables. Based on these assessments, a detailed list of sensor types, placements, and specifications will be generated to ensure that the system captures the most relevant data for each site.

3.1.3.2 Sensor Installation Plan

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
Sensor Installation Plan	A comprehensive plan will be developed for sensor deployment, outlining the optimal placement of sensors, potential power supply

	options (e.g., solar or grid power), communication networks, and data management strategies. It is essential that sensors are situated in locations that yield the most crucial data for monitoring purposes. The plan will encompass the design of a network architecture to guarantee the dependable transmission of data to the cloud platform. Power configurations will be optimised in order to ensure the continuous operation of sensors, even in remote or challenging environments.
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3.1.3.3 *Data Quality Control and Calibration*

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
Data Quality Control and Calibration	To guarantee the veracity and dependability of the data obtained from the sensors, calibration routines and quality control protocols will be established. These protocols will encompass regular sensor calibration, in addition to automated systems for the assessment of sensor accuracy and performance over time. In the event of anomalies or malfunctions, automatic alarms will be triggered, facilitating prompt intervention and rectification.

3.1.3.4 *Communication Protocols for Data Transmission*

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
Communication Protocols for Data Transmission	Secure and reliable communication channels will be established to transmit data from in-situ sensors to the TerraFusion Platform. These protocols will include LoRaWAN, Wi-Fi, or satellite communications, depending on the specific requirements of each site. Backup systems will be in place to ensure data transmission continuity, even in the event of network outages or other disruptions.

3.1.3.5 *Ongoing Maintenance and Support*

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
Ongoing Maintenance and Support	A long-term maintenance protocol will be established with the objective of ensuring the continued functionality of the sensors. Such procedures will include routine inspections, remote diagnostics and software updates, all of which will be coordinated through a

	centralised support system. A maintenance schedule will be devised with the objective of reducing downtime and guaranteeing that the sensors remain fully operational throughout their operational lifespan.
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3.1.3.6 *Data Integration and Cloud Management*

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
Data Integration and Cloud Management	Once collected, the data from in-situ sensors will be integrated into the TerraFusion Platform, where it will be combined with aerial imagery and satellite data for comprehensive analysis. This integration will facilitate advanced analytics, such as geo-hazard detection, and support decision-making processes related to mining operations. By linking in-situ data with EO and aerial imagery, operators will be able to make informed decisions based on real-time information.

3.1.4 Connection to existing databases and other data sources

Description	The Data Integration Component will be responsible for developing connectors between various data sources and the TERRAFUSION Platform. This component will be responsible to integrate data from existing sources, in situ sensors, drone-acquired data throughout the project duration. Data will be first imported through this component to the platform, then they will be transformed to a harmonized common format that will be used throughout the system. Data then will be available to other TERRAVISION components through interfaces supporting the openEO standard.
Building blocks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Ingestion Endpoints Multiple interfaces will be provided (REST APIs, data streams, and manual upload) for data upload to the TerraFusion Platform. • Data Source Connectors Specialized connectors will be developed to interface with various data sources, including existing repositories, in situ sensors, and drones. • Data Harmonization Layer

	<p>Transforms incoming data from various sources into a standardized format for system-wide use.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Validation and Quality Control Ensures the integrity and quality of ingested data through validation rules and error handling. • Monitoring and Logging Tracks the performance and usage of data integration processes, including activity logging and performance metrics.
<p>Interfaces</p>	<p>Various data Ingestion Endpoints will be developed, based on what each data source supports. Any protocol that is needed will be supported, prioritizing REST API endpoints wherever possible.</p>

Figure 6. Functional view of Connection to existing databases and other data sources

3.1.4.1 Data Ingestion Endpoints

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
<p>Data Ingestion Endpoints</p>	<p>This service will provide multiple interfaces for data upload to the TerraFusion Platform. It includes REST API endpoints that allow data upload using standard HTTP methods, enabling a common integration with various systems. Also, data stream connectors will be included if needed to support real-time data ingestion using technologies like</p>

	Kafka for continuous data streams. Additionally, a user-friendly manual upload interface will be available for uploading historical data if it is not possible to upload them using any of the above protocols, ensuring comprehensive data coverage.
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3.1.4.2 *Data Source Connectors*

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
Data Source Connectors	Specialized connectors will be developed to interface with various data sources. Custom integrations, with TERRAVISION components that they may already have their own interfaces, will be developed to extract historical and ongoing data from them. These connectors will be designed with flexibility in mind, and will support different data formats, protocols, and transmission methods that each specific data source may provide.

3.1.4.3 *Data Harmonization Layer*

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
Data Harmonization Layer	This service will be responsible to transform incoming data from various sources into a standardized format for system-wide use. A data transformation engine will convert incoming data to a common, internally-used lightweight format, ensuring consistency across all data types. Regarding data that will be available to other components, OpenEO specification will be used to make them available promoting interoperability with other geospatial systems. Schema mapping will be implemented to map various input data schemas to the unified internal data model, facilitating smooth data integration regardless of the original format.

3.1.4.4 *Data Validation and Quality Control*

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
Data Validation and Quality Control	This service will ensure the integrity and quality of ingested data. It will apply predefined validation rules to check data consistency and maintaining high data standards throughout the system. Error

handling mechanisms will manage and report any issues encountered during data ingestion or harmonization, allowing for quick resolution of data-related problems.

3.1.4.5 *Monitoring and Logging*

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
Data Harmonization Layer	This service tracks the performance and usage of the data integration processes. It will include logging that records all data ingestion and harmonization activities, providing a detailed audit of system operations. Performance metrics will be continuously monitored, offering visibility of the data processing stage and helping identify possible bottlenecks.

3.2 Data Processing and Integration

This section focuses on data pre-processing, harmonization, and integration across various data types, ensuring they are ready for analysis.

3.2.1 Development of Synergistic Framework of Tools and Methods for Producing ARD and Indices

Description	<p>The TERRAVISION project will implement an ARD framework, composed of a suite of services and libraries structured as microservices. This framework is designed to facilitate the analysis of raw satellite imagery. These satellite images will be sourced through the CDSE architecture.</p> <p>All processes within the ARD framework will adhere to a consistent spatial resolution and utilize standardized data formats based on Common Architecture for Remote Sensing Data (CARD4L) such as Geographic Tagged Image File Format (GeoTIFF), Network Common Data Form (NetCDF), Geographic JavaScript Object Notation (GeoJSON) among others, ensuring compatibility with GIS and remote sensing software. Additionally, comprehensive metadata will be included with each dataset to provide detailed information about data quality and other relevant attributes.</p>
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A state-of-the-art study will be conducted to evaluate and integrate existing components, enabling the construction of a robust and reliable workflow for satellite image analysis.

The Open Source projects to be used will be:

Open Data Cube (<https://www.opendatacube.org/>) facilitates the organization of satellite data into a standardized format, supporting the indexing of large datasets to make querying and accessing data more efficient. It offers tools for reprojecting data to different coordinate systems, resampling data at different resolutions, automatically detecting and masking cloud-covered areas in satellite imagery and standardizing different datasets for compatibility in analysis. Each step will be annotated according to the TERRAVISION ontology, indicating the process followed by the data.

PyWPS (Python Web Processing Service <https://pywps.org/>) enables remote execution of data processing tasks via web services, the automation of data pre-processing workflows, integration with other GIS tools and libraries for data manipulation and pre-processing and allows the execution of custom Python scripts for specific pre-processing tasks. The workflow will be semantically annotated to track the process each data element has undergone.

GRASS (Geographic Resources Analysis Support System <https://grass.osgeo.org/>) GIS supports a wide range of data formats for import and export, comprehensive tools for reprojection and resampling of spatial data, tools for cleaning and transforming spatial data, capabilities for handling and pre-processing temporal data, and extensive support for both raster and vector data pre-processing. Every transformation and pre-processing action will be annotated with the TERRAVISION ontology to ensure transparency and traceability of the data processing steps.

Rasterio (<https://rasterio.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>) offers efficient reading and writing of raster data, tools for reprojection of raster datasets to different coordinate systems, applying masks to raster data to exclude certain areas from analysis, tools for scaling, cropping, and transforming raster data, and managing and updating raster metadata. The processes performed on the data will be semantically annotated to provide a clear record of the steps taken.

GDAL (Geospatial Data Abstraction Library <https://gdal.org/en/stable/>) converts geospatial data between various formats, provides tools for reprojection and resampling of geospatial data, extracts subsets of data based on spatial and attribute queries, attaches geographic coordinates to data, combines

multiple datasets into a single file, and supports extensive pre-processing of both raster and vector data. Each operation will be annotated semantically according to the TERRAVISION ontology to document the process followed.

EO-learn detects and masks clouds in satellite imagery, provides tools for resampling data both spatially and temporally, extracts features from raw data for analysis, standardizes and scales data for ML applications, and uses techniques to enhance and augment the dataset for better analysis. All pre-processing steps will be annotated to indicate the process followed by each data element.

Based on the pre-processing capabilities outlined above, a set of services will be selected and implemented using these libraries.

All processes will be semantically annotated in accordance with the TERRAVISION project's ontology to ensure comprehensive tracking and transparency of the data's processing history.

Building blocks

- **Data Ingestion and Indexing**
This service organizes satellite data into a standardized format and indexes large datasets, making it efficient to query and access the data.
- **Reprojection, Resampling and Data Warping**
This service reprojects data to different coordinate systems, resamples it at various resolutions and warps raster datasets to ensure alignment with other geospatial information.
- **Cloud and Data Masking**
This service automatically detects and masks cloud-covered areas in satellite imagery.
- **Data Normalization, Scaling and Format Conversion**
This service standardizes, scales and converts datasets into compatible formats for analysis.
- **Raster Data Handling**
This service handles efficient reading, writing, scaling, cropping and transforming of raster data.
- **Data Extraction and Georeferencing**
This service extracts subsets of data based on spatial and attribute queries and attaches geographic coordinates to data.
- **Data Merging, Stacking, and Image Augmentation**
This service combines multiple datasets into a single file, integrates various data layers and applies augmentation techniques to enhance and increase the robustness of the dataset for better analysis.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pixel and Feature Level Models This service extracts features from raw data for analysis, transforming raw satellite imagery into meaningful variables that can be used in ML and statistical models (this module is described in a separated document). • Semantic Annotation This service semantically annotates all data based on an ontology developed for the TERRAVISION project.
Interfaces	The ARD will be a set of microservices-based architecture deployed using docker. Different containers will communicate via RESTful APIs, allowing for modular development, scaling and maintenance.

Figure 7. Functional view of ARD

3.2.1.1 Ingestion and Indexing

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Data Ingestion and Indexing	This service organizes satellite data into a standardized format and indexes large datasets, making it efficient to query and access the

	<p>data. It ensures that all incoming satellite images are properly formatted and catalogued for easy retrieval and analysis.</p> <p>Satellite images will be gathered from CDSE as well as other processed data such as ARD formats.</p>
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3.2.1.2 *Reprojection, Resampling, and Data Warping*

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Reprojection, Resampling, and Data Warping	<p>This service reprojects data to different coordinate systems, resamples it at various resolutions, and warps raster datasets to ensure alignment with other geospatial information. This integration ensures that all satellite imagery is compatible with other datasets and can be analysed uniformly, regardless of the original data source.</p>

3.2.1.3 *Cloud and Data Masking*

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Cloud and Data Masking	<p>This service automatically detects and masks cloud-covered areas in satellite imagery, as well as applying other custom masks to exclude irrelevant or noisy data from analysis. This ensures that analyses are based on clear, unobstructed views of the Earth's surface and focus only on regions of interest.</p>

3.2.1.4 *Data Normalization, Scaling, and Format Conversion*

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Data Normalization, Scaling, and Format Conversion	<p>This service standardizes, scales, and converts datasets into compatible formats for analysis. It adjusts data values to a common scale, facilitates comparisons, and ensures that the data is in a format suitable for integration with various GIS and remote sensing software.</p>

3.2.1.5 *Raster Data Handling*

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Raster Data Handling	This service handles efficient reading, writing, scaling, cropping, and transforming of raster data. It ensures that raster datasets are correctly manipulated and updated for further analysis.

3.2.1.6 *Extraction and Georeferencing*

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Data Extraction and Georeferencing	This service extracts subsets of data based on spatial and attribute queries and attaches geographic coordinates to data, ensuring the accurate spatial representation of each data point. This allows users to focus on specific areas or attributes of interest within large datasets and ensures that data from different sources are correctly aligned.

3.2.1.7 *Data Merging, Stacking, and Image Augmentation*

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Data Merging, Stacking, and Image Augmentation	This service combines multiple datasets into a single file, integrates various data layers, and applies augmentation techniques to enhance and increase the robustness of the dataset for better analysis

3.2.1.8 *Pixel and Feature Level models*

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Pixel and Feature Level Models	This service extracts features from raw data for analysis. It transforms raw satellite imagery into meaningful variables that can be used in ML and statistical models (this module is described in a separated document).

3.2.1.9 Semantic Annotation

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Semantic Annotation:	This service semantically annotates all data based on an ontology developed for the TERRAVISION project. It tracks and documents the process followed by each data element, ensuring transparency and traceability of the data processing steps. This annotation includes metadata about the origin, transformations, and quality of the data, making it easier to understand and use in subsequent analyses. This service includes detailed metadata to describe the quality and characteristics of the data. It documents the origin, processing steps, and quality metrics of the satellite imagery, providing users with essential information about the data they are using.

3.2.2 Super Resolution (SR) Modelling Architectures

Description	<p>The SR service will provide advanced tools for SR and multisensory fusion to deliver spatially augmented datasets to the TERRAVISION services. Four individual spatial augmentation tools will be developed:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Sentinel-2 SR will be used to increase the resolution of the coarser bands of Sentinel-2 to the resolution of the finer bands (i.e., from 20 m & 60 m to 10 m), while preserving the integrity of their spectral resolution.2. Thermal sharpening techniques will be applied to spaceborne thermal data, such as Sentinel-3 Sea and Land Surface Temperature Radiometer (SLSTR) to produce land surface temperature maps of higher spatial resolution.3. SR and pansharpening techniques to enhance the spatial resolution of PRISMA (PRecursore IperSpettrale della Missione Applicativa) hyperspectral images from 30m to 5m by integrating the high spatial resolution panchromatic band available in PRISMA datasets.4. Multisensory data fusion techniques to improve the spatial resolution of coarse resolution spaceborne environmental parameters, such as ground-level air pollutants concentration from Sentinel-5P.
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<p>Building blocks</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <p>Sentinel-2 SR</p> <p>Develop globally applicable SR models that can be used with Sentinel-2 Levels 1B and 2A products for any Sentinel-2 scene, especially those captured over the areas of interest. The models will generate Sentinel-2 datasets composed with 12 bands, all having a common spatial resolution of 10 m.</p> <p>PRISMA Hyperspectral pansharpener</p> <p>PRISMA hyperspectral data will be fused with the panchromatic image, which is simultaneously acquired by the PRISMA sensor, to produce a high spatial resolution hyperspectral cube with the 5 m spatial resolution of the panchromatic image while preserving the spectral information of the hyperspectral data.</p> <p>Thermal sharpening</p> <p>Various types of spaceborne thermal datasets will be fused with high spatial resolution multispectral data, such as Sentinel-2 to provide higher spatial resolution thermal datasets.</p> <p>Multisensor data fusion</p> <p>Estimation of ground-level concentrations of various air pollutants at a higher resolution of 1 km by fusing Sentinel-5P vertical column concentrations with higher spatial resolution proxy data such as topographic and meteorological data.</p>
<p>Interfaces</p>	<p>The TERRAVISION SR Service will be deployed using docker and will utilize a REST API to deliver spatially augmented data back to the TerraFusion Platform. The output format will be in image formats.</p>

Figure 8. Functional view of TERRAVISION Super-Resolution Service

3.2.2.1 Sentinel-2 SR

The capabilities of Sentinel-2 make it a valuable tool for a wide range of mining-related applications, including exploration, environmental management, and rehabilitation. Its high resolution, frequent revisits, and broad spectral range provide essential data that support various aspects of mining operations and their environmental impacts. The Sentinel-2 twin satellites are equipped with an optical payload that includes visible, near-infrared, and shortwave infrared sensors. This payload comprises 13 spectral bands: 4 bands at 10 m, 6 bands at 20 m, and 3 bands at 60 m spatial resolution. Reasons for capturing images at different spatial resolutions include limitations in storage and transmission bandwidth, enhanced signal-to-noise ratio in certain bands due to larger pixels, and bands tailored for specific purposes that do not necessitate high spatial resolution (e.g., atmospheric correction). However, spatial data analysis requires all available data to have a common and the highest spatial resolution possible to extract more detailed and accurate information. Given the wide range of services that Sentinel-2 data can support, the initial component of the SR service aims to enhance the spatial resolution of the coarser bands (i.e., 20 m and 60 m) to match the resolution of the finer bands (i.e., 10 m).

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Sentinel-2	Develop globally applicable SR models that can be used with Sentinel-2 Levels 1B and 2A products for any Sentinel-2 scene, especially those captured over the areas of interest. The models will output Sentinel-2 datasets composed of 12 bands having a common spatial resolution of 10 m. Large training datasets will be created to train models that can super-resolve random Sentinel-2 images without retraining. This service will get new Sentinel-2 images acquired over the TERRAVISION mining sites whenever they become available on the CDSE. The trained SR models will spatially enhance the acquired images and provide as an output 12 Sentinel-2 bands at a higher and common spatial resolution of 10 m. The super-resolved Sentinel-2 images will be stored as GeoTIFF images on the TerraFusion Platform.

3.2.2.2 PRISMA Hyperspectral Pansharpening

Hyperspectral images with a large number of spectral bands have gained immense attention in mineral exploration and geological mapping. When capturing an image, hyperspectral sensors face trade-offs between spectral and spatial resolution due to the limited incident energy available. As a result, hyperspectral sensors can provide images with high spectral resolution but low spatial resolution. On the other hand, panchromatic sensors can offer data with high spatial resolution but only a single spectral band. The relatively low spatial resolution of hyperspectral images results in relatively poor performance in various remote sensing applications, necessitating hyperspectral images with both high spatial and spectral resolution. To overcome this issue, the Hyperspectral Precursor and Application Mission (PRISMA) has been designed to

simultaneously acquire both a hyperspectral image with a spatial resolution of 30 m and a panchromatic image with a spatial resolution of 5 m that can be fused to produce a hyperspectral image having a higher spatial resolution of 5 m. This building block will provide efficient tools for the pansharpening of the PRISMA hyperspectral images with their counterpart panchromatic images.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION PRISMA Hyperspectral Pansharpening	Pansharpening techniques will be provided to spatially augment the 250 spectral bands acquired from the hyperspectral sensor onboard PRISMA. This service will provide 5 m spatial resolution PRISMA hyperspectral images acquired over the TERRAVISION mining sites. The images will be obtained from the TerraFusion Platform, and the spatially enhanced images will be saved back to it as GeoTIFF images.

3.2.2.3 *Thermal Sharpening*

Thermal infrared (TIR) remote sensing images are valuable for estimating the distribution of land surface temperature. These images can be a useful tool for various aspects of mining operations, such as exploration, safety monitoring, and environmental management. Thermal data can help identify surface temperature anomalies associated with specific minerals or geological formations. They can also be used to monitor the stability of mine slopes and tailing dams by detecting temperature variations that may indicate potential failure zones or water seepage. Additionally, thermal remote sensing is useful for evaluating the effectiveness of land reclamation efforts by monitoring soil temperature and moisture content, which are indicators of vegetation health and soil recovery. However, the Sentinel constellation contains only one thermal sensor onboard Sentinel-3 satellites with a coarse spatial resolution of 1 km, which is insufficient for the above-mentioned mining-related applications. Therefore, there is a need for an efficient thermal sharpening tool to enhance the spatial resolution of the Sentinel-3 thermal data to a level that is suitable for mining-related applications.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Thermal Sharpening	The service will include several thermal sharpening methods for enhancing the spatial resolution of Sentinel-3 thermal data by fusing them with higher spatial resolution multispectral data, such as Sentinel-2 images. These techniques determine the relationship between the Land Surface Temperature (LST) and the independent multispectral features at the coarse resolution of thermal images and then the extracted relationship is applied to the original multispectral data to estimate the high spatial resolution LST. The tool will offer spatially enhanced Sentinel-3 thermal data whenever pairs of cloud-free Sentinel-3 and Sentinel-2 images are acquired over the areas of

interest. The Sentinel images will be acquired from CDSE, and the spatially enhanced image outputs of GeoTIFF format will be stored on the TerraFusion Platform.

3.2.2.4 *Multisensory Data Fusion*

Monitoring air pollutant concentrations is a crucial part of responsible and sustainable mining practices. It is essential at mining sites to ensure the health and safety of workers, protect the environment, comply with regulations, optimize operations, manage risks, and maintain good community relations. The modelling of the spatial distribution of air pollutants is complex to obtain due to the sparse network of ground-level air quality monitoring stations. The Sentinel-5P mission can map most locations on Earth frequently and provide information about the vertical column density of air pollutants, but this is different from the ground concentrations measured by ground stations.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Multisensory Data Fusion	The service will include multisensory data fusion models for estimating the spatial distribution of surface air pollutant concentrations at a spatial resolution of 1 km. Sentinel-5P data retrieved from the CDSE will be fused with proxy data, such as meteorological and topographic data, and the higher-resolution ground-level concentration will be estimated by training ML models with in-situ surface measurements. The required data will be collected daily from CDSE and the TerraFusion Platform, and the derived spatially enhanced data will be stored back on the TerraFusion Platform as GeoTIFF images.

3.3 Analytical Models and Tools

3.3.1 Pixel and Feature Level Models and Analysis

Description	<p>The primary goal is to develop separate models for pixel-level and feature-level analysis of satellite images to identify region boundaries and extract main features such as edges, corners, and textures. These models will aid in the classification of objects within the images.</p> <p>This architectural design outlines the development of pixel-level and feature-level models for analysing satellite imagery. The approach focuses on using deep learning techniques for pixel-wise analysis and</p>
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	<p>traditional ML classifiers for feature extraction and object classification. The models will be evaluated and optimized using advanced hyperparameter tuning and ensemble methods, with an emphasis on interpretability and explainability to ensure reliable predictions.</p>
<p>Building blocks</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feature extraction model • Based on satellite imagery and data extracted during the ARD. • Pixel-Level Model • The pixel-level model is designed to analyse satellite images at the granular level, identifying boundaries and distinguishing between different regions within the imagery. • Object Segmentation level Model • This service utilizes the Segment Anything Model (SAM) or similar to accurately segment objects within satellite imagery. • Language level Model • This service utilizes a Vision Model Large (VLM) to automatically generate detailed descriptions of objects found in satellite imagery
<p>Interfaces</p>	<p>The building blocks will be a set of microservices-based architecture deployed using docker. Different containers will communicate via RESTful APIs, allowing for modular development, scaling and maintenance.</p>

Figure 9. Functional view of Pixel and Feature Level Models and Analysis

3.3.1.1 Feature Extraction Model

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Feature extraction model	Based on satellite imagery and data extracted during the ARD, this module will be designed to process satellite images and identify essential characteristics such as edges, corners, and textures. It will use computer classic computer vision algorithms

3.3.1.2 Pixel-Level Model

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Pixel-Level Model	The pixel-level model is designed to analyse satellite images at the granular level, identifying boundaries and distinguishing between different regions within the imagery. This model employs deep learning techniques, specifically leveraging Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to capture intricate spatial hierarchies and patterns in the image data. The process begins with the input of pre-processed satellite images, which are then passed through multiple convolutional layers to detect low-level features such as edges and textures.

3.3.1.3 Segmentation Level Model

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Object Segmentation level Model	This service utilizes the SAM or similar to accurately segment objects within satellite imagery. SAM is a powerful deep learning model designed to segment objects of interest in images, regardless of their scale, shape, or appearance. The Object Segmentation Using SAM service applies advanced ML techniques to identify and delineate objects within satellite images. The service leverages SAM's robust segmentation capabilities to process large-scale imagery and generate precise object boundaries. This segmentation is crucial for various applications such as land cover classification, urban development monitoring, agricultural analysis, and environmental assessment.

3.3.1.4 Language Level Model

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Language Level Model	This service utilizes the Large Language and Vision Assistant (LLaVA) VML to automatically generate detailed descriptions of objects found in satellite imagery. LLaVA VML is an advanced vision-language model designed to understand and describe visual content, providing comprehensive and context-aware descriptions of objects. The Object from Mine Description Using VML service leverages the capabilities of VML to analyze segmented objects in satellite images and produce rich, natural language descriptions. This service enhances the understanding of satellite imagery by translating visual information into descriptive text, which can be valuable for reporting, documentation, and further analysis.

3.3.2 RM Spectral Knowledge Base

Description	The RM Spectral Knowledge Base service will provide AI-based tools for grade estimation of target commodities from hyperspectral images of scanned drill core samples and spaceborne and airborne hyperspectral data. Three individual grade estimation tools will be developed:
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	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Spaceborne hyperspectral CoreSmart: Hyperspectral images acquired from new hyperspectral missions, such as PRISMA and EnMAP, will be used to predict the grade of the target RMs using the new AI-based CoreSmart approach trained with the hyperspectral data acquired from the respective spaceborne sensor. 2. Airborne hyperspectral CoreSmart: This version of the AI-based CoreSmart grade detector will provide higher spatial resolution target RM grade estimations from the high spatial resolution airborne hyperspectral data provided by Task 5.2 and T6.2. 3. CoreSmart predictor: This tool will allow the estimation of the chemical composition of drill cores from data acquired from drill core hyperspectral scanners and the original AI-based CoreSmart predictor.
<p>Building blocks</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spaceborne hyperspectral CoreSmart Develop AI-based grade estimation models that can be used with data acquired from the EnMAP and PRISMA spaceborne hyperspectral sensors, especially those captured over the areas of interest. The models will output metal-grade maps with the spatial resolution of the input hyperspectral images. • Airborne hyperspectral CoreSmart Develop AI-based grade estimation models that can be used with data acquired over the areas of interest from airborne hyperspectral sensors. The models will output metal-grade maps with the spatial resolution of the input hyperspectral images. • CoreSmart predictor for drill cores Develop AI-based grade estimation models that can be used with drill core hyperspectral scanning data. The models will output image files.
<p>Interfaces</p>	<p>The TERRAVISION RM Spectral Knowledge Base Service will utilize a REST API to deliver metal-grade maps of various spatial resolutions and metal-grade estimations from hyperspectral scanning data of drill cores to the TerraFusion Platform. The output format will be in image format.</p>

Figure 10. Functional view of TERRAVISION Raw Material Exploration Service

3.3.2.1 *Spaceborne hyperspectral CoreSmart*

The modern spaceborne hyperspectral missions EnMAP and PRISMA can provide higher spatial resolution hyperspectral data than their predecessors. This is an opportunity to identify the ability of the CoreSmart approach to detect grade from satellite hyperspectral data. These data will be fed to the CoreSmart predictor model, which will be trained on the chemical compositions of ground samples obtained with an XRF device to provide grade estimation of target raw materials.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Spaceborne hyperspectral CoreSmart	The service will provide grade maps of target raw materials estimated from spaceborne hyperspectral data acquired from PRISMA and EnMAP satellite missions. The input hyperspectral data will be obtained from the TerraFusion Platform, and the grade maps will be stored as GeoTIFF images on the Terravision cloud platform.

3.3.2.2 Airborne hyperspectral CoreSmart

Airborne hyperspectral sensor data can provide very high spatial resolution hyperspectral data compared to space-borne sensors. This is an opportunity to identify the ability of the CoreSmart approach to detect grades from airborne satellite hyperspectral data. These data will be fed to the CoreSmart predictor model, which will be trained with the chemical compositions of ground samples to provide grade estimation of target raw materials.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Airborne hyperspectral CoreSmart	The service will provide grade maps of target raw materials estimated from airborne hyperspectral data provided by Task 5.2 and 6.2. The input hyperspectral data will be obtained from the TerraFusion Platform, and the grade maps will be stored as GeoTIFF images on the TerraFusion Platform.

3.3.2.3 CoreSmart Predictor for Drill Cores

This service will provide the opportunity to estimate grades directly from drill cores in a non-destructive way by scanning drill cores with hyperspectral scanners. The hyperspectral scanning data will be the input of the AI-based CoreSmart model to estimate the grades.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION CoreSmart Predictor for Drill Cores	This service will provide grade estimations from drill core hyperspectral scans. The input scan data will be obtained from the TerraFusion Platform, and the grade estimations will be stored as image files on the TerraFusion Platform.

3.3.3 Raw Material Exploration Service

Description	The workflow for raw material exploration involves collecting and analysing data at regional and local scales using diverse sources like hyperspectral, multispectral, geological, and geophysical data to identify potential mineralization areas. Regional exploration relies on medium spatial resolution data and is conducted over large areas to identify regions with the potential to contain mineral resources. On the other hand, local exploration focuses on targeting mineral deposits within a smaller geographical area by using higher spatial resolution data.
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	<p>The spectral library is a critical resource for automated lithology and mineral mapping and hydrothermal alteration zone identification by comparing unknown spectral signatures with its reference signatures. Existing spectral data from open spectral libraries will be gathered and integrated into an open database to create a reliable and comprehensive spectral library. Subsequently, high spatial and spectral resolution data collected from spaceborne, and airborne sensors will be used to identify characteristic features such as indicator minerals, rock types and hydrothermal alterations by comparing their measured spectral curves with the library's reference spectra.</p> <p>Integrating the produced characteristic feature maps with geological and geophysical data can help identify areas where mineralization is more likely to occur and target specific areas for further exploration. Prospectivity maps will be conducted at regional and local scales to identify promising greenfield regions for further exploration.</p> <p>Finally, to indicate the most promising areas for exploitation, automated identification of metal grades directly from high spatial resolution hyperspectral data will be performed.</p>
<p>Building blocks</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spectral Library Development Creation of a reliable and comprehensive spectral library, which gathers all the available spectral data scattered around various spectral libraries and stored in various formats. • Characteristic Geological Feature Mapping Identification of geological features such as lithological units, alteration types, structures and indicator minerals with knowledge-based and data-driven methods. • Prospectivity Modelling Provision of prospectivity maps at regional and local scales by analysing the characteristic feature maps with geological and geophysical data to identify promising greenfield regions for further exploration. • Processibility Mapping Provision of metal grade maps to inform about the spatial variability of metal grades in the TERRAVISION demonstrators' mining areas.
<p>Interfaces</p>	<p>The Terravision RM Exploration Service will utilize a REST API to deliver raw material exploration data to the TerraFusion Platform. The output format will primarily be in image formats, which include geological feature, mineral prospectivity and metal</p>

concentration maps derived from hyperspectral and multispectral data.

Figure 11. Functional view of TERRAVISION RM Exploration Service

3.3.3.1 Spectral Library Development

Hyperspectral sensors with many contiguous spectral bands having narrow bandwidths, allow accurate identification and discrimination of various materials based on absorption features within their spectra. Interpreting airborne and spaceborne hyperspectral data requires reference spectra of well-characterized materials. Therefore, a spectral library will be developed to serve as a knowledge base for the characterization and mapping of critical RM.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Spectral Library	A comprehensive library of spectra data obtained from various existing spectral libraries will be developed to use spectral features for remote identification and mapping of critical RMs. Every spectral data instance in the library will contain its origin (i.e., the initial spectral library), metadata describing the measurements and details of measurement procedures, along with photographs of the samples, impurities, and other important information about the sample's characteristics and composition.

3.3.3.2 *Characteristic Geological Feature Mapping*

One of the fundamental steps in mineral exploration is localizing the geological features related to target ore deposits. Depending on the nature of the deposits, these geological features might include lithological units, alteration types, tectonic structures and indicator minerals.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Geological Feature Mapping	Various geological features will be identified using remote sensing data with knowledge-based and data-driven methods. The developed spectral library will provide the reference spectral signatures for mapping rock types, hydrothermal alteration zones and indicator minerals.

3.3.3.3 *Prospectivity Modelling*

Prospectivity maps are tools used in mineral exploration to predict the likelihood of finding mineral deposits in greenfield areas. These maps combine various geological, geophysical, geochemical and remote sensing data to identify regions with a high potential for mineralization.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Prospectivity Modelling	Prospectivity maps will be developed by carefully selecting the independent features related to the target ore deposit type. These features will include characteristic geological feature maps, geophysical and geological data. Various ML/DL models will be trained using the values of each independent feature at known mineral occurrences across the exploration areas to analyze the spatial relationships between known mineral deposits and the various features. Afterwards, these spatial relationships will be applied to unknown areas to quantify the mineralization potential.

3.3.3.4 *Processability Mapping*

Metal concentration (grade) mapping illustrates the distribution of metal concentrations in mining areas. Identifying areas with the highest-grade material allows prioritizing the extraction of the wealthiest portions of the ore body, thereby allowing better production scheduling and enhancing profitability. Additionally, metal grade maps can define the lowest economically viable metal content (cut-off grade) for mining and processing, thus preventing wasteful extraction of low-value material and reduced processing efficiency.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Processability Mapping	Metal concentrations will be estimated using the AI-based grade estimation tools provided by the RM Spectral Knowledge Base service. The maps will be created and updated as new hyperspectral remote sensing data becomes available.

3.4 Platform Services and Outputs

This section includes end-user services and mapping tools as part of the TERRAVISION platform.

3.4.1 Surface Deformation Mapping and Monitoring

Description	Advanced multi-temporal analysis of Copernicus Sentinel-EO data for measuring and tracking surface motion over time with millimetre-level accuracy
Building blocks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Discovery and Access Ingests and stores metadata about available data, manages the actual data storage, and provides tools for users to search, discover, and visualize data. It also manages secure access to data. Data Processing Facilitates communication between different processing components, manages workflows for processing data, and provides access to various data processing services, supporting additional functionalities as needed. Front-End Services Acts as the main interface for users to interact with the platform, including specific web applications designed for different use cases. It supports interactive visualization of ground motion time series. Interferometric (IFG) service IFG processing of Copernicus Sentinel-1 mission data for generation of stacks of differential interferograms used as inputs for subsequent time series analysis. Persistent Scatterers Interferometry (PSI) service Multi-temporal interferometric time series processing of satellite Radar imagery based on the PSI technique. 3D Geometric Decomposition service

	<p>Combination of ascending and descending Line-of-Sight PSI measurements for calculation of actual vertical (up) and E-W motion components.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Temporal Decomposition service Decomposition of PSI displacement time series into trend, seasonal and residual motion components supporting further interpretation of measurements. • Automatic Reporting service Generation of a brief readable report highlighting obtained measurements and providing basic information for the overview of the PSI measurement.
<p>Interfaces</p>	<p>The proposed solution comprises several blocks, some of which are already operational, while others will be integrated into the GEP. The interoperability with the TerraFusion Platform will be designed to ensure a seamless execution of GEP services directly from the TerraFusion Platform, allowing users to access, visualize and exploit final measurements and products once processing is complete:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Discovery The platform provides a SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog (STAC) API that allows users to programmatically search and retrieve data. • Data Processing The application execution engine provides the web service interface (OGC API Processes) that is called by the front-end services to execute specific data processing applications.

3.4.1.1 *Data Discovery and Access*

The Data Discovery and Access component is a critical part of the GEP platform. Its primary purpose is to enable users to efficiently search, discover, and access the vast amounts of EO data ingested into the system. This component ensures that the data is organized, searchable, and retrievable in a user-friendly manner, supporting the platform's goals of providing accessible and usable data for various applications.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
<p>GEP Data Discovery and Access</p>	<p>The implementation of the Data Discovery and Access component involves several key elements designed to facilitate effective data search and retrieval:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Indexing and Search

PostgreSQL, provided as a service by the cloud provider, is used to index and store the metadata catalogued during the ingestion process. PostgreSQL's robust querying capabilities enable fast and efficient search operations. Users can perform queries based on various criteria such as time, location, and data type.

- **API Access**

The platform provides APIs that allow users to programmatically search and retrieve data. These APIs adhere to industry standards, ensuring broad compatibility and ease of use. The STAC API implementation with FastAPI, using PostgreSQL SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog (PgSTAC) for backend storage, ensures efficient data querying and retrieval.

- **Visualization Tools**

Integrated visualization tools enable users to preview and interact with the data directly within the platform. This includes map-based interfaces and other graphical tools that help users understand and analyze the data. The Web Map Tile Service (WMTS) API, powered by a Tiler backend, ensures accurate and responsive data visualization.

- **Signed URL Service**

For data stored in S3-compatible object storage, the platform uses a signed URL service to securely provide access to the data. This service generates temporary URLs that allow users to download data directly from storage.

3.4.1.2 *Data Processing*

The Data Processing component of the GEP platform is designed to transform raw EO data into valuable information and insights. This component enables users to perform various data processing tasks, including data cleaning, transformation, analysis, and visualization. The primary purpose of this component is to provide a robust and scalable infrastructure that supports both systematic and on-demand processing of EO data, ensuring that users can derive meaningful insights and actionable information from the data.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
GEP Data Processing	<p>The implementation of the Data Processing component involves several key elements designed to facilitate efficient and scalable data processing:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Event Bus The Argo Events event bus, powered by Apache Kafka, handles the communication between different parts of the system. It ensures that data is seamlessly passed from the ingestion

component to the processing workflows, and it also handles notifications and triggers for processing tasks.

- **Processing Workflow Engine**

The processing workflow engine, implemented using Argo Workflows, manages the execution of complex processing pipelines. These pipelines are defined using the Common Workflow Language (CWL) and orchestrate various tasks such as data validation, transformation, and analysis.

- **Application Execution Engine**

The application execution engine provides the web service interface (OGC API Processes) that is called by the front-end services to execute specific data processing applications. It also calls the Processing Workflow Engine to execute EO applications defined as application packages. The application execution engine has two distinct functionalities: deployment and execution.

The event bus is responsible for handling the communication and data flow between different components of the data processing pipeline. Argo Events uses Apache Kafka to manage the flow of messages and events, ensuring that data is efficiently routed and processed in a timely manner.

The processing workflow engine manages the execution of complex data processing workflows. It uses Argo Workflows to define and orchestrate these workflows, ensuring that tasks are executed in the correct order and that dependencies are managed.

The Application Execution Engine provides the web service interface (OGC API Processes) that is called by the front-end services to execute specific data processing applications. It manages the execution of these applications, ensuring they are accessible via standardized APIs, and it calls the Processing Workflow Engine for executing complex workflows.

3.4.1.3 *Front-End Services*

The Front-end Services component of the GEP platform is designed to provide users with intuitive and accessible interfaces to interact with the platform's capabilities. These services include the GEP Portal and geobrowser as well as an interactive tool for ground motion time series visualization. The primary purpose of the Front-end Services is to enable users to efficiently and effectively utilize the platform's resources and capabilities through user-friendly interfaces.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
GEP Front-end Services	<p>The implementation of the Front-end Services involves several key elements designed to ensure a seamless and efficient user experience:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GEP Portal A web-based portal that provides users with access to data discovery, retrieval, and visualization tools. The portal offers an intuitive user interface with clear categorizations, filters, and search capabilities. • User Authentication and Authorization Secure access to front-end services through integrated authentication and authorization mechanisms. • Visualization Clients Integrated visualization clients access the Tiler backend in the Data Discovery and Access component to convert geospatial raster data into web-friendly map tiles for display on web applications. • Time Series Viewer A dedicated web application for users focusing on ground motion measurements analysis, that supports: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Dynamic visualization Users can visualize the average velocity of ground movements in a dynamic fashion on a map, enhancing the understanding of spatio-temporal patterns. Measurement points are automatically clustered in space according to the visualization scale. ○ Customizable data representation Through layer selection, look up tables and color scale adjustments, users can tailor the data presentation to meet specific analytical needs. ○ Advanced data filtering Filtering of points according to velocity thresholds, facilitating focused analyses on areas of interest. ○ On-the-fly time series visualization ○ Plotting of displacement time series for specific points, generating statistics for areas of interest, and visualizing mean velocity values and surface elevation values along geographic transects. ○ Export of time series data

Users can export the time series of terrain motion measurements on the map over the area of interest in CSV format and in CovJSON formats.

Figure 12. GEP System Components

3.4.1.4 IFG service

Differential Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar (DInSAR) is a well-established and mature technique used to map surface motion, particularly in areas susceptible to ground deformation, such as mining sites. The technique utilizes radar signals from satellites, such as the Copernicus Sentinel-1 mission, to detect subtle changes in the Earth's surface between Radar acquisitions. DInSAR works by comparing radar images (interferograms) taken at different times from the same location in space. By measuring the phase difference between these images, namely differential interferograms, DInSAR can detect ground displacement with centimetre accuracy. One of the key advantages of Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) sensors is its ability to penetrate clouds and operate independently of daylight. Unlike optical sensors, SAR can capture data under all weather conditions and during both day and night, ensuring consistent and reliable observations. Additionally, satellite SAR can cover wide areas with a relatively low cost compared to other geodetic approaches. The extensive spatial coverage and cost-effectiveness of SAR make it an ideal tool for monitoring large-scale ground deformation over mining sites, providing continuous and comprehensive data that can be used to ensure the safety and efficiency of mining

operations. This service generates a number of differential interferograms, collocated into interferometric stacks. These stacks serve as the inputs for a more detailed time series analysis, allowing for continuous monitoring of surface motion over extended periods.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION IFG	<p>This block involves the interferometric processing of Copernicus Sentinel-1 data for generation of differential interferograms which are used in subsequent time series analysis for the measurement of surface motion.</p> <p>Inputs: Copernicus Sentinel-1 Single Look Complex (SLC) products accessed from various dissemination sources.</p> <p>Outputs: Interferometric stacks; non-usable intermediate product for the PSI service (Block 5).</p>

3.4.1.5 *PSI service*

PSI represents a significant advancement in radar remote sensing, greatly improving the accuracy of conventional DInSAR measurements. While traditional DInSAR techniques provide valuable insights into surface motion, PSI enhances these capabilities by achieving millimetre-level precision. This is made possible by focusing on "persistent scatterers"—stable, highly reflective objects on the Earth's surface, such as buildings or natural features that consistently return strong radar signals. By monitoring these scatterers over time, PSI can detect even the smallest changes in surface movement. The technique involves analysing a large stack of radar images collected over an extended period. This multi-temporal approach allows PSI to capture subtle, gradual shifts in the surface with remarkable accuracy. The core of PSI processing involves creating interferograms from pairs of radar images (see description in Block 4), which measure the phase difference between them to detect displacement. This sophisticated method provides a high-resolution view of surface motion, overcoming limitations of the DInSAR approach. Execution of PSI algorithms demand significant technical expertise, while extensive processing requirements in terms of computational power are also necessary, especially when dealing with large volumes of radar imagery. The integration of PSI on cloud computing platforms has alleviated many of these challenges. In the context of mining, PSI offers a cost-effective monitoring solution. By tailoring the technique to the changing topography of a mine, PSI helps in managing the dynamic nature of mining operations, ensuring precise monitoring and timely interventions to address potential issues.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION PSI	<p>Interferometric time series analysis of surface motion along the satellite's Line-of-Sight (LoS) using Copernicus Sentinel-1 radar data and the PSI technique.</p> <p>Inputs: Interferometric stacks (output of Block 5)</p> <p>Outputs: Comma Separated Value (CSV) file</p>

Figure 13. Schematic diagram showing the IFG and PSI operational services integrated on the GEP

code;	latitude;	longitude;	vel;	vs;	coh;	height;	inc_angle;	D20150404;	D20150416;	D20150428;	...
1;	40.231686;	23.72987;	-0.39;	0.44;	0.85;	50.33;	0.676172;	0.0;	10.15;	-10.15;	...
2;	40.232704;	23.722376;	-0.95;	0.45;	0.81;	50.52;	0.676749;	0.0;	10.3;	-10.3;	...
3;	40.2337;	23.715092;	-0.8;	0.38;	0.73;	61.56;	0.677298;	0.0;	9.72;	-9.72;	...
4;	40.242413;	23.650858;	0.31;	0.3;	0.7;	141.27;	0.682141;	0.0;	4.82;	-4.82;	...
.
.
.

Figure 14. Sample of the CSV outputs from the PSI service, including geolocation information, surface motion rates with corresponding accuracies, and displacement time series

3.4.1.6 Geometric Decomposition service

The 3D geometric decomposition of LoS measurements based on PSI measurements is a post-processing technique that transforms data from both ascending and descending satellite orbits into distinct vertical (up/down) and horizontal (east-west) motion components. This method is essential because LoS measurements alone combine vertical and horizontal displacements, making it challenging to interpret surface motion. By utilizing different viewing angles from the two satellite orbital tracks, this decomposition isolates these components, for a clearer understanding of surface motion. For mine operators, the result of this decomposition is a more straightforward product that facilitates easier interpretation of ground deformation data. Rather than working with LoS measurements, the derived vertical and E-W components, where

applicable, offer direct insights into the specific directions of ground movement, enhancing decision-making in managing mining operations.

Figure 15. Schematic diagram illustrating the principle of geometric decomposition of ascending and descending spaceborne interferometric surface motion measurements (left) and the resulting displacement components (right)

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION 3D Geometric Decomposition	<p>This block is dedicated to the post-processing of PSI measurements, enabling the calculation of actual motion components, namely the vertical (upward or downward) and horizontal (E-W) motion components, from initial LoS data.</p> <p>Inputs: Separate PSI CSV files for ascending and descending satellite tracks (output of Block 5)</p> <p>Outputs: CSV file; consistent output format as per the PSI service</p>

3.4.1.7 Temporal Decomposition service

Surface motion can be influenced by various phenomena that operate on different time scales. Separating these temporal motion patterns is essential for accurately attributing observed movements to specific deformation sources. By analysing the evolution of motion over time, including any accelerations, users can better address and mitigate potential issues. The proposed service, which decomposes motion data into long-term trends and seasonal signals, enables the identification of both multi-annual deformations and seasonal variability, in addition to the detection of abrupt changes that may require immediate attention.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Temporal Decomposition	<p>A post-processing service for PSI data segments displacement time series into distinct components, such as temporal trends, seasonal variations, and residual motion. This division enhances the interpretation of causative deformation sources by clearly distinguishing different patterns of surface motion.</p> <p>Inputs: PSI CSV files (output of Blocks 5 and 6)</p> <p>Outputs: CSV file; consistent output format as per the PSI service</p>

Figure 16. Example of temporal decomposition of observed surface motion time series into various components.

3.4.1.8 Automatic Reporting service

Inspecting PSI measurements typically involves using specialized visualization and analysis tools, which can complicate the actual exploitation of measurements. Although some EO platforms have integrated visualization features, the steps involved, especially for the interpretation of results, can still be cumbersome and not always optimized for users outside of technical fields. A high-

level overview of PSI measurements, emphasizing areas with significant motion, can be beneficial. Such summaries allow users to quickly assess whether further, more detailed investigation is necessary. Additionally, direct access to time series data for locations of interest provides valuable, immediate insights into the phenomena being monitored and highlights any accelerating motions that may require prompt action. This streamlined approach enhances the practical utility of PSI data, making it more accessible and actionable for professionals in different domains.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Automatic Report	<p>Creation of a document providing an interpretation-ready summary of PSI measurements, highlighting key statistical properties, measurement accuracies, and significant motion clusters within the area of interest, along with their corresponding displacement time series. This report offers a clear and concise description of surface motion for high-level decision-making.</p> <p>Inputs: PSI CSV files (outputs of Blocks 5, 6 and 7)</p> <p>Outputs: CSV file; consistent output format as per the PSI service</p>

3.4.2 Extraction Rate in Opencast Mining; Changes in Stockpile Volumes

Description	<p>The extraction rate service in opencast mining will harness advanced technologies such as computer vision, object detection, 3D modelling, surface reconstruction, and volume estimation to deliver precise measurement and analysis of stockpile volumes, excavation progress, and overall extraction rates. It will begin with the systematic collection and annotation of images of excavators, dump trucks, and vegetation from TERNA MAG mines, ensuring data consistency for training a cutting-edge object detector. Using data from these specific mines, the service aims to mitigate potential domain-gap issues, crucial for developing a robust detection system. The deployment of sensors such as RGB cameras, LiDARs, and drones will facilitate comprehensive scanning missions, generating 3D point-clouds via LiDAR scans or photogrammetry. These point-clouds will form the foundation for refining volumetric estimation algorithms.</p> <p>The creation of an orthophoto from these point-clouds will enable for both manual and automatic selection of Regions of Interest (ROI). Terrain normalization processes will help identify and exclude non-stockpile objects, aligning their Z-coordinates with ground</p>
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morphology to eliminate interference in volumetric calculations. The service will offer precise volumetric estimation for designated regions (representing stockpiles) within the 3D point-cloud, as well as comparative volumetric estimation by tracking volume changes across the entire mine or quarry over time.

Ultimately, the extraction rate will be determined by assessing volume changes between two georeferenced point-clouds representing the same area at different times, such as one week apart, offering a detailed and accurate measure of extraction activity within the mining operation. The extraction rate will likely be provided in a JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) file, which will include details such as the latitude/longitude of the associated point-clouds, their timestamps, and other relevant information.

<p>Building blocks</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Object Detector Selection of a state-of-the-art object detector and application of transfer learning utilizing collected data from the site. • 3D Point-cloud Generation Generation of 3D point-cloud originating either from LiDAR-scans or RGB-images via photogrammetric pipelines. • Orthophoto Generation Creation of an orthophoto from photogrammetric or LiDAR-based point-clouds, enabling manual or automatic selection of the ROI. • ROI Selection Provision of a drag-and-drop interface for manual ROI selection or automatic ROI selection based on the object detector's output. • Terrain Normalization Identification of non-stockpile objects on the orthophoto, mapping them to corresponding regions in the 3D point-cloud, and adjustment of Z-coordinates within those regions to respect the surrounding ground morphology, thereby eliminating interference in volumetric estimation. • Absolute Volumetric Estimation Estimation of the volume of a specific region (representing stockpiles) within the 3D point-cloud. • Relative Volumetric Estimation Calculation of volume differences between two point-clouds representing the same region with different timestamps, with accuracy dependent on effective terrain normalization.
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Interfaces

Describe here the mechanism (e.g., restapi) and the output format (e.g., image, vector) that will be provided back to TerraFusion Platform by this service. Modify appropriately for components that do not give output directly to the platform but to another component.

Figure 17. Functional view of TERRAVISION Extraction Rate in Opencast Mining Service

3.4.2.1 Object Detector

An opencast mining location includes a variety of objects that can be categorized and analysed for valuable insights. Automating this process is crucial for the Extraction Rate Service. The available data dictate the specific approach to be followed for object detection. Given that drones are primarily employed to capture data through aerial surveys of the opencast mine, and that drone photogrammetry is the predominant method for point-cloud generation, a 2D object detector is considered more suitable for this application. The raw images captured during the drone flights at the TERNA MAG mines will be utilized for training and validation, while the generated orthophoto will be used for testing and real-time evaluation. Thus, through this data-driven approach, objects specific to the mining context are identified such as excavators, dump trucks, and vegetation. By automatically identifying each object's category and determining its precise location within 2D images, the Object Detector's output can then be mapped onto the 3D point-cloud corresponding regions. This mapping allows the utilization of the detector's output in tasks such as ROI selection, terrain normalization, and volumetric estimation, thereby optimizing the overall process of the Extraction Rate Service.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Object Detector	A state-of-the-art pre-trained real-time object detection model will be selected and finetuned through transfer learning to detect objects of specific categories of interest. Drone RGB images (2D) from the field, obtained from the data-acquisition block, will be annotated, and utilized to form train, validation, and test sets. The neural network will be finetuned to distinguish categories such as stockpiles, vegetation, trucks etc. depending on the task at hand. During inference time, the orthophoto will be divided into tiles while preserving the original aspect ratio of the orthophoto. These tiles will be processed by the fine-tuned neural network. The ability to identify the category of an object as well as its exact location in the orthophoto will enable the automatic selection of a ROI and will also allow for terrain normalization post-process techniques to be performed more accurately.

3.4.2.2 3D Point-cloud Generation

Point-clouds, crucial for volumetric estimation and extraction rate analysis in opencast mining, can be generated through two primary methods: direct acquisition using LiDAR and photogrammetric pipelines. LiDAR involves using laser pulses to measure distances to the mine's surfaces, producing highly accurate 3D representations of the terrain and excavation sites. Photogrammetry constructs point-clouds by analysing and triangulating overlapping images captured from different angles, typically using drones or cameras. These techniques provide detailed spatial data essential for precise volume calculations and monitoring extraction rates, enabling efficient planning, resource management, and operational optimization in open-pit mining.

Although licensed tools are available for many aspects of point-cloud processing, our goal is to develop an in-house solution in an effort to bypass the constraints and costs associated with commercial software, ensuring greater control and customization. Furthermore, creating our own solution enables effortless integration with the TERRAVISION EO platform, enhancing flexibility and efficiency in our workflows.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION 3D Point-cloud Generation	This block involves the creation of a detailed 3D representation of the mining area using various data sources. This process can use aerial and drone images, and LiDAR scans collectively referred to as Input Data. By processing these inputs, the system generates a dense and accurate point-cloud, capturing the spatial coordinates of surface points. This 3D model is essential for accurately measuring

terrain changes, calculating volumes, and analysing the extraction rate in opencast mining operations. Both the absolute and the relative volume estimation blocks rely upon raw or cropped versions of the 3D point-clouds.

3.4.2.3 *Orthophoto Generation*

The Orthophoto Generation block is a crucial component of our extraction rate service, designed to enhance the accuracy and effectiveness of object detection. This module generates orthophotos from LiDAR-based or photogrammetric point-clouds, bridging a critical gap in data representation, particularly for LiDAR datasets that typically lack accompanying orthophotos. By converting 3D point-cloud data into high-resolution 2D orthophotos, this module provides detailed and georeferenced raster images essential for precise object detection and analysis.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Orthophoto Generation	<p>The orthophoto will be generated from either LiDAR-based or photogrammetric point-clouds for object detection purposes. It is particularly important to create orthophotos from LiDAR-based point-clouds, as these typically lack the accompanying orthophotos that are available in photogrammetric pipelines. The orthophoto shall respect the aspect ratio defined by the X and Y range of the 3D point-cloud, ensuring that each pixel in the raster image has equal dimensions in both directions to maintain geometric accuracy and spatial integrity. Accurate representation is vital for reliable object detection and analysis, as any discrepancies in scale or proportions could lead to errors in interpreting spatial relationships and measurements. The higher the resolution of the orthophoto, the greater the performance of the object detector but at the cost of greater memory requirements and inference time. To ensure accuracy, the orthophoto will be evaluated using GIS tools by measuring objects with known dimensions or overlaying the raster on a Google satellite layer to confirm alignment.</p>

3.4.2.4 *ROI Selection*

The ROI Selection building block is a critical component in the Extraction Rate Service, as it isolates specific areas within the original 3D point-cloud that are relevant for volumetric analysis. The ROI selection is designed to be both robust and flexible. An automatic selection tool leverages the output of the Object Detector, identifying and isolating regions containing specific objects of interest. In addition to the automated tool, a user-interface for manual ROI selection is also provided. This enables end-users to enhance the automatically selected areas, providing greater control and precision. The potential collaboration between these two methods ensures high-

quality and accurate ROI selection, which is crucial for precise volumetric estimation and the subsequent calculation of the extraction rate.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION ROI Selection	Provided an orthophoto, the user will be offered the option of proceeding to the volume estimation modules either through manual or automatic selection of a ROI. In the first case, the user will be presented with a resized version of the orthophoto, allowing for the selection of non-overlapping bounding boxes that define the area(s) of interest. The high-resolution orthophoto is resized to fit the user's screen, ensuring ease of use and efficient selection. In the latter case, the object detection building block will be utilized to identify candidate areas of the orthophoto containing objects of a certain category of interest. Regardless of the process followed for the selection of the ROI, a mapping to the 3D point-cloud is then performed for further processing steps to be applied.

3.4.2.5 *Terrain Normalization*

The terrain normalization block is crucial for accurate volumetric analysis in 3D point-clouds. It identifies and adjusts the Z-coordinates of non-terrain objects, such as vegetation and vehicles, which are considered noise because they distort the true volume measurements of the terrain. By realigning these objects' elevations to match the surrounding ground surface, this block ensures that the calculated volume reflects only the terrain itself, free from interference. If these objects were entirely removed, it would introduce large holes in the data, and it would complicate the accurate modelling of the terrain surface. Therefore, by normalizing rather than removing these objects, we maintain a continuous surface that supports more reliable and accurate volumetric analysis.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Terrain Normalization	Initially, the ROI selection module will identify regions within specified categories of interest (e.g., vegetation, dump trucks, excavators, etc.) or any other regions defined by the user. These selected regions in the orthophoto will be mapped to their corresponding 3D regions in the point-cloud. These regions are treated as noise since their volume would inaccurately contribute to the overall volume calculation. The module adjusts the Z-coordinates of the detected non-stockpile objects to align with the ground morphology, thereby eliminating their interference in volumetric calculations.

3.4.2.6 *Absolute Volume Estimation*

In the realm of EO, precise volume estimation of specific sections within a quarry or mine is critical for efficient resource management and operational planning. The Absolute Volume Estimation module, a key component of our extraction rate service, is meticulously designed to deliver accurate volume calculations for designated sections of a 3D point-cloud obtained by mapping 2D areas from the orthophoto back to their corresponding 3D world counterparts. This functionality is paramount for scenarios where understanding the volume of individual stockpiles is essential, while the overall extraction rate for the entire site remains beyond the scope of such localized analysis.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Absolute Volumetric Estimation	This block will estimate the volume of stockpiles within a cropped 3D point-cloud representing a specific section of the scanned mine or quarry. The cropped point-cloud will occur from the 2D to 3D mapping after the ROI selection. It will start by isolating the plane points from the stockpile points, thereby simplifying further analysis. Next, in the presence of multiple stockpiles in the cropped point-cloud, it will identify and separate individual stockpiles. For every stockpile, statistical outliers will be meticulously removed to enhance accuracy, and extra noise will be filtered out using methods like Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise (DBSCAN) clustering. Surface reconstruction will be carried out using techniques such as the Ball Pivoting Algorithm, Poisson, or Delaunay Triangulation. The volume of each stockpile will be then calculated based on the reconstructed surface. Finally, the total volume will be obtained by summing the volumes of all individual stockpiles.

3.4.2.7 *Relative Volume Estimation*

The Relative Volume Estimation block is a vital component of the extraction rate service contributing to the TERRAVISION EO platform, designed to enhance the monitoring and management of mining operations. By accurately calculating changes in volume for specific georeferenced regions over time, this module provides crucial insights into extraction rates, supporting informed decision-making and optimized resource management. This high-level analysis enables operators to track material removal, ensuring efficient and sustainable exploitation of resources.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Relative Volumetric Estimation	Estimating the relative volume change between two point-clouds with different timestamps is essential for monitoring alterations in a

scanned area. To accomplish this, we will compare point-clouds provided by TERNAMAG (currently generated via drone photogrammetry), the main demonstrator of the extraction rate service, using their documented volume change as a reference. We will explore two primary methods: the mesh-based approach and the point-cloud raster-grid approach. The mesh-based method involves reconstructing surfaces, calculating the volume of each mesh by summing the tetrahedral volumes formed from the mesh triangles, and comparing the total volumes of the two meshes. Although accurate, this method is computationally demanding and relies on having watertight meshes. In contrast, the point-cloud raster-grid approach projects the point-clouds onto a grid and computes volume differences based on height variations. This method is anticipated to be faster and avoids the complexities associated with mesh reconstruction but requires careful grid resolution selection to maintain accuracy and reliability. We will thoroughly evaluate the benefits and limitations of each method. Eventually, the volume change rate can be determined by dividing the estimated volume change by the time interval between the two point-cloud captures, such as one week.

3.4.3 Primary and Secondary RM Maps

Description

Mineral exploration phases are developed by mining industries to find ore deposits which obtention is economically and technically viable. The mining exploration phase is one of the most relevant and costly in terms of average investment return rate, especially if large areas are assessed. Geophysical, geological and geochemical data are required to realize an accurate mineral exploration. However, the field work needed to obtain these data constitutes a major part of the expenses in the mineral exploration phase. As a result, various mining studies are currently combining field data (in-situ data) with remote sensing datasets since these datasets have a low cost and they can play an essential role to define areas with a high mineral exploration potential.

Thus, the workflow for primary and secondary raw material maps involves a combination between EO systems and in-situ data. These data will be obtained from the previous TERRAVISION tasks and work packages stored in the TerraFusion Platform.

Primary raw material map

To develop a map which shows the main mineral types and compositions with remote sensing tools it is necessary to assess the absorption features in the optical electromagnetic spectrum. These spectral signatures allow us to identify different materials on the earth surface from remote sensing data. One of the main limitations of using remote sensing data for mineral exploration is the lack of depth penetration. This underlines the necessity of combining remote sensing data with field data. The evaluation of the absorption features in the optical electromagnetic spectrum, as well as the collection of the field data should be done in previous tasks. VITO's role in this task will be the integration of the EO data with the field data to deliver maps as the ones shown on figure 1 and 2.

To develop a complete primary raw material map Sentinel-2 data will be used and integrated with airborne magnetic data, airborne time domain electromagnetic data, geochemistry from stream sediments and rocks, and finally lithology and structural geological data. As it was mentioned previously, these field data (electromagnetic, geochemical and lithological data) will be collected and provided on previous TERRAVISION tasks. The field data needed for the development of the primary raw material maps should be defined along the project based on the requirements of the end-users. Apart from the field data selection and collection, the remote data should be treated too. Firstly, the remote data should be pre-processed and secondly the field data (airborne geophysical data, geochemical data and geological field observation data) will be transfer to a geo database to prepare it for application of data integration techniques. These two steps (pre-processing and database development) should be done on previous TERRAVISION tasks.

Finally, VITO will use the geo database developed within the project to integrate and validate the data on an imagery interpretation.

Secondary raw material map

In the same way than the primary raw material maps to create a secondary raw material map it is needed to combine remote sensing data with in-situ data. In this project we propose to combine Sentinel-2 images with geochemical data to assess the distribution of elements and develop maps by means of a multivariate geostatistical estimation method called Co-kriging. VITO's role in this task will be develop statistical analysis and realize the co-kriging method.

Building blocks	<p>Primary raw material map:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pre-processing remote sensing data
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Sentinel-2 will be used to obtain multispectral remote sensing data. These data will be processed in order to do a scene classification, an atmospheric correction and a subsequent conversion into Level-2A data. This multispectral remote sensing data will be collected in previous tasks and it will be needed by VITO to be integrated with the in-situ data.

- **Processing remote sensing data**

Apply feature extraction methods to classify remote sensing images obtained previously. For the primary raw material map the feature extraction methods that will be applied are band ratios, Principal Component Analysis (PCA), and lineaments. In the same way as the pre-processing phase, the processing of remote sensing data should be done before this task. VITO will need to receive band ratios, PCA and lineaments data to develop the image classification and the data integration.

- **Image classification**

The Self-Organizing Maps (SOM) and the Support Vectors Machine (SVM) methods will discriminate the lithological and structural units present in Sentinel-2 images.

- **Data Integration**

Geological, geophysical, and geochemical maps are integrated with Sentinel-2 data to obtain the primary raw material map. Quantified primary raw material stocks will be visualized on a map in a format that can be used on the TERRAVISION platform.

Secondary raw material map:

- **Pre-processing data**

Sentinel-2 can measure the Earth's reflected radiance in 13 spectral bands. In the pre-processing phase, all the Sentinel-2 bands will be stacked and resampled at the 10x10m spatial resolution by means of the nearest neighbour method. This step should be done on previous tasks and the experts should choose the proper bands based on the materials that the end-user is interested in.

- **Statistical analysis**

A statistical analysis should be done to assess the geochemical element variation. The geochemical statistics of the selected elements for the secondary raw material map should be contrasted with the optimal band ratios for these elements. VITO will develop the statistical analysis with the geochemical element data obtained by other partners in previous tasks.

- **Spatial variation of selected elements**

Cross-variograms and co-regionalization models should be developed to analyse the spatial correlation between the band

	<p>ratios selected and the chosen elements. Finally, it is proposed to apply the Co-Kriging method to estimate the data on the unknown areas. VITO will assess the spatial variation of the selected elements once we received the remote sensing data and the field data obtained on previous tasks. Quantified secondary raw material stocks will be visualised on a map in a format that can be used on the TERRAVISION platform.</p>
<p>Interfaces</p>	<p>The output format will be in image formats, which includes detailed multispectral signatures and mineral composition maps (Figure 1 and 2).</p>

Figure 18. Functional view of primary and secondary raw material maps. VITO tasks correspond to the blue blocks.

Figure 19. Example of primary raw material map. Source: Abdolmaleki, M., Rasmussen, T. M., & Pal, M. K. (2020)

Figure 20. Example of secondary raw material map (2.a). Source: COP-Piles project (<https://eitrawmaterials.eu/eit-rm-academy/rawmatcop/post-docs/>)

3.4.3.1 Primary raw material map. Pre-processing remote sensing data

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
Primary raw material map. Pre-processing remote sensing data	<p>Sentinel-2 will be used to obtain multispectral remote sensing data. These multispectral data should be processed first to “clean” the data. Sen2Cor will be the tool applied for this pre-processing phase. This tool will do a scene classification, an atmospheric correction and a subsequent conversion into Level-2A data.</p> <p>This multispectral remote sensing data will be collected in previous tasks and it will be needed by VITO to integrated with the in-situ data.</p>

3.4.3.2 Primary raw material map. Processing remote sensing data

Once the pre-processing corrections are done the feature extraction methods should be applied to the data. As it was mentioned previously, mineral type and composition can be determined by assessing their absorption features in the optical electromagnetic spectrum. That is why select a proper and efficient method to extract mineral spectral features is fundamental for this project.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
Primary raw material map. Processing remote sensing data	<p>The main objective of feature extraction is to reduce the data space dimensions without loss of significant information, once the data is reduced it will be classified in different spectra. In this project the features extraction methods proposed to be applied are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Band ratios This technique uses band ratios as proxies for mineral groups. • Principal Component Analysis (PCA) Multivariate statistical technique which is applied to enhance and separate spectral signatures from the background. • Lineaments This technique consists of contrasting spatial features, as brightness, to discriminate the geological structures on the study area. <p>The processing remote sensing data phase should be done before this task. VITO will need to receive band ratios, PCA and lineaments data to develop the image classification and the data integration.</p>

3.4.3.3 Primary raw material map. Image classification

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
Primary raw material map. Image classification	<p>Supervised and unsupervised image classification methods will be applied to discriminate lithological and structural units, from the Sentinel-2 images, in the study areas. The selected methodologies are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Self-Organizing Map (SOM) A SOM consist of neurons organized in a low dimensional grid, these neurons are connected to others by a neighborhood relation, and theses relations indicates the topology or a map. SOM methodology entails the application of standard k-means clustering procedures which will help to define a map of the study area. It is essential to contrast each cluster generated with the known geological data to develop an accurate map. Support Vector Machine (SVM) This is one of the most widely used classifiers for remote sensing images. SVM is a supervised classifier, these kinds of classifiers need training samples to give results, the SVM methodology in this project will use image pixels which represent regions of known features to train the algorithm and generate a map.

3.4.3.4 Primary raw material map. Data Integration

The fact that Sentinel data has no depth penetration highlight the necessity of integrate these data with depth information data. To solve this lack of depth penetration data, this project will integrate geophysical data with the Sentinel data, what will provide accurate and complete primary raw material maps.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
Primary raw material map. Data integration	<p>To develop the data integration on this project a Fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process (FAHP) should be applied. This process is based on three principles which are construction of a hierarchy, priority setting, and logical consistency. The FAHP compares several input layers which derived from three different data types, in this case the data types are remote sensing data, and geophysical data which consist of airborne magnetic data and electromagnetic data. These three different data types are integrated and validated to create reliable maps.</p>

3.4.3.5 *Secondary raw material map. Pre-processing data*

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
Secondary raw material map. Pre-processing data	<p>Sentinel-2 can measure the Earth's reflected radiance in 13 spectral bands. In the pre-processing phase, all the Sentinel-2 bands will be stacked and resampled at the 10x10m spatial resolution by means of the nearest neighbour method.</p> <p>This step should be done on previous tasks and the experts should choose the proper bands based on the materials that the end-user is interested in.</p>

3.4.3.6 *Secondary raw material map. Statistical analysis*

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
Secondary raw material map. Statistical analysis	<p>A statistical analysis should be done to assesses the geochemical element variation. The geochemical statistics of the selected elements for the secondary raw material map should be contrasted with the optimal band ratios for these elements.</p> <p>VITO will develop the statistical analysis with the geochemical element data obtained by other partners in previous tasks.</p>

3.4.3.7 *Secondary raw material map. Spatial variation of selected elements*

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
Secondary raw material map. Spatial variation of selected elements	<p>Cross-variograms and co-regionalization models should be developed to analyse the spatial correlation between the band ratios selected and the chosen elements. Finally, it is proposed to apply the Co-Kriging method to estimate the data on the unknown areas.</p> <p>VITO will assess the spatial variation of the selected elements once we received the remote sensing data and the field data obtained on previous tasks.</p>

3.4.4 Dynamic Hazard Maps

Description

The Dynamic Hazard Maps service for the mining sector will integrate advanced technologies and huge datasets to predict and hence manage the ground stability risks in a way that revolutionizes safety standards. The share of fatal work accidents in the EU high-standard mining sector may be relatively low, but often the nature of mining accidents results in severe consequences. This service will deal with the challenge of predicting events of slope or underground instability by combining numerous dynamic and static factors into a comprehensive hazard mapping tool. Its ambition is to yield a reliable state-of-the-art Industry 4.0 system as a service supporting early, location-based targeted decision-making.

To achieve this, Dynamic Hazard Maps will use diverse data sources and advanced analytics techniques. These factors are dynamic and include Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar (InSAR), ground-based radar, topographic updates, weather prediction, other instrumentation monitoring, and blasting. They provide real-time measurements and high-precision parameters on such ground deformation, weather conditions, and environmental parameters. Continuous updates from these shall be recorded into the GIS layers so that hazard maps will always reflect the latest conditions on the ground. This allows for real-time monitoring with timely responses to possible impending hazards. These are the foundational parameters of the hazard mapping tool and include geotechnical parameters, stratigraphy, structural geology and rock mass quality. The above parameters will define the geologic and mechanical behaviour of soil and rock, which is very important in modelling and predicting ground stability. By overlaying this static data with dynamic information, like upcoming factors such as weather, these hazard maps can give a more holistic and realistic assessment of the risk level in different mining areas.

The system integrates data from in-situ measurements, satellite imagery and analyses of past rock or soil failures using ML. Should historical data be deficient, numerically advanced modelling techniques will be used to simulate ground deformation at the onset of failures. The system incorporates the use of ground sensors, ground-based radars and analysis of satellite imagery for continuous monitoring and detection of ground movements. Numerical models will be applied for simulation and prediction of ground stability, coupled with dynamic maps and a user interface to support decisions in the case of the mine staff. This information, derived from the dynamic hazard maps, would not only improve safety in predicting

and preventing issues of ground stability but would also allow interaction with every part of the TERRAVISION Project's main platform. In this way, hazard maps might be integrated with other services or tools provided by the TERRAVISION Project in a comprehensive approach to mining safety and risk management. Such integration would ensure strengthened decision-making with the help of AI, remote sensing and IoT technologies, which would mitigate potential risks and enhance operational safety for the mining sector.

Building blocks

- **Dynamic Factors**
 - InSAR: Used for detecting and measuring ground movements with the usage of Satellite Images.
 - GbSAR (Ground Based Synthetic Aperture Radar): Provides real-time monitoring of ground stability, using the Hydra-X SAR.
 - Topo Update: Ensures that topographic data is accurate at all times, by updating the topography with the usage of UAVs, in a weekly or monthly bases.
 - Weather Prediction: Weather prediction involves the use of meteorological data to forecast weather conditions that could impact ground stability. This includes predicting heavy rainfall, temperature extremes, and other climatic factors that might influence geotechnical conditions.
 - Pore Water Pressures: Vibrated wired piezometers will provide data about the water pressures distribution inside the rock mass.
 - Additional Instrumentation: Extensometers, triaxial tilt meters, optical displacement sensors, will provide data from underground mine of TERNAMAG.
 - Blasting: Possible usage of geophones will depict the impact of mining operations on ground stability.

- **Static Factors**
 - Geotechnical Parameters: Provides fundamental data for modelling and predicting ground stability. These data are related to the elasticity, strength, unit weight and porosity of the geomaterials.
 - Structural Modelling: Identifies potential weaknesses and failure planes within the rock mass, by depicting the the geometrical characteristics of discontinuities in 3D.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Rock Mass Quality: Determines the overall stability of the rock mass, by quantifying the spatial distribution of the quality/strength of the rock mass. ○ Stratigraphy: Identifies and understands the distribution of different rock types and their geometric relationship.
<p>Interfaces</p>	<p>The Dynamic Hazard Maps service will use a REST API for the seamless transfer of time-dynamic hazard data into the TerraFusion Platform. Data is provided in several formats, focusing on vector and raster layers that represent different geospatial and temporal aspects of ground stability. These layers will involve high-resolution maps with indications of potential hazard zones, ground movements shown in time-series data from InSAR and ground-based radar, water pressure distribution models and updates on topography. Bringing this wide variety of datasets into the TerraFusion Platform ensures that all relevant information about hazards can be made available and usable to support real-time decision-making and risk management in mining operations.</p>

Figure 21. Functional view of TERRAVISION Dynamic Hazard Maps service

3.4.4.1 *InSAR - Dynamic*

InSAR is a remote sensing method, which exploits radar satellite images to detect ground deformation. This technology is currently a vital tool in monitoring geophysical changes on Earth's surface, as it can detect even millimetre – scale movements over extensive regions.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION InSAR Technology	<p>The phase differences between radar images at different times can be interpreted to form a measurement of the ground's displacement (these are InSAR measurements). This is important for the recognition and monitoring of small-scale deformation that may be key indicators of subsurface failure pose risks such as surface degradation often resulting in landslides or subsidence in mines.</p> <p>The parameters concerned with this block are displacements or subsidence measured (in mm) over time. Data delivery is made within *.csv file format, where the file contains the full time series analysis results and metadata derived from the monitoring algorithm. There is an ESRI shapefile showing the reflectors, the points on the ground that do not change during the time of observation. Each point in the ESRI shapefile contains only displacement rates and measures of quality derived from the *.csv file.</p>

3.4.4.2 *GbSAR (Ground Based Synthetic Aperture Radar) - Dynamic*

Powerful as well, ground-based radar systems are used to monitor movements of surface and subsurface. Ground Based Radar systems work by sending radio waves and analysing the signals reflected to detect movements on the ground. For cases which require continuous real-time monitoring, radar technology is especially beneficial.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION GbSAR Technology	<p>Real – time monitoring systems that use radar technology provide information on ground stability, detect ground movement and potential slope instability. Through regular monitoring, radar technology allows for quick identification of hazardous conditions and managing risks through immediate interventions.</p> <p>The parameters concerned with this block are the displacements (in mm) over time. The data are normally given as a time series and usually stored in a *.csv file. Besides that, spatial data showing which</p>

areas of the slope are moving can be in several vector formats - e.g. *.shp or *.dxf files - or sometimes in raster format, like an ESRI Grid.

3.4.4.3 Topography Update - Dynamic

A topographic update refers to the process of maintaining and refreshing elevation and surface data aligned with real-time terrain state. High – resolution topographic maps are often generated using LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging) or UAVs (Unmanned Aerial Vehicles) commonly.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Topographic Update	<p>Topographic data update is essential for up-to-date hazard mapping. This component ensures that topographic information is updated frequently to enable accurate modelling and analysis of ground conditions so that hazard assessments and decision-making processes are reliable.</p> <p>Mining activities cause topography to be one of the changing parameters through time. The data related to this block involves 3D models created from photos taken by UAVs. File formats will include but not limit to *.obj, ESRI Grid Files, ESRI ASCII files, and point clouds in *.LAS or *.LAZ formats.</p>

3.4.4.4 Weather Prediction - Dynamic

Weather forecasting uses meteorological data to forecast weather conditions that may potentially affect land stability. Forecasting rainfall, temperature swings and other weather patterns are some of the conditions that may affect geotechnical conditions.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Weather Prediction	<p>The weather prediction is integrated into hazard mapping to predict and respond to ground movements that may be caused from wet weather. This component predicts severe weather events, assisting proactive risk management by enabling advance notice for avoiding or reducing the effects of such incidences on mining operations.</p> <p>Weather data will typically be time series recorded in comma-separated files including temperature, precipitation, and humidity parameters.</p>

3.4.4.5 Pore Water Pressures – Dynamic

The data collected by vibrated wired piezometers will offer insight into the distribution of water pressures within the rock mass.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Pore Water Pressures	This block refers to the connection of the weather conditions and their effect on slope stability to water pressure distribution within the rock mass during hazard analysis. The water pressure, which changes due to the rain infiltration, may change the effective stress and consequently the active forces that are responsible for causing instability. Therefore, monitoring the temporal distribution of water pressures at different depths in a slope is essential for landslide risk evaluation.

3.4.4.6 Additional Instrumentation - Dynamic

This block refers to several in-situ sensors and monitoring equipment, measuring different environmental and geotechnical parameters. The instruments shall monitor continuously such factors as soil moisture, groundwater level, seismic activities or other parameters relevant to the test site conditions.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Geotechnical Monitoring	Application of various types of instrumentation in monitoring allows comprehensive coverage of prevailing conditions that affect ground stability. The real acquisition of data on several parameters enables this component to thoroughly understand the dynamic environment for the accurate and timely execution of hazard evaluations. The water pressures are measured in kPa and are usually time series saved in *.csv files.

3.4.4.7 Blasting - Dynamic

Blasting in mining is a common process which involves breaking rock using explosives. Monitoring and analysis of the effects of blasting activities are critical for ascertaining that such operations do not compromise ground stability.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Blasting	<p>This module allows quantification of the effects that blasting will have on the surrounding geology to identify potential blasting – related hazards. It ensures the hazard maps produced in risk assessment procedures, fully incorporate the impact of such operations, furthering good mining practice and effective risk management.</p> <p>Blasting Vibrations data will typically be time series recorded in *.csv files. The parameter measured is the frequency (Hz) of the vibrations in relation to time.</p>

3.4.4.8 *Geotechnical Parameters - Static*

Geotechnical parameters are defined as the characteristics, which describe the physical properties of soil and rock, with the latter determining their mechanical behaviour. Examples of such properties include shear strength, cohesion, porosity, among others, which are important for understanding ground stability.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Geotechnical Properties	<p>These data form the basis for modelling or prediction of ground stability and therefore, form the very basis of hazard assessment. They allow the construction of reliable models able to simulate the ground behaviour for various conditions, thus helping to identify and mitigate potential hazards.</p> <p>Several parameters can be assessed, one common being the Uniaxial Compressive Strength, expressed in MPa and obtained through tests conducted on site. Another parameter is the basic friction angle, which can also be identified from tests on site and are expressed in degrees. These data are typically expressed as scalars in the form of quantities to describe the measure of each parameter.</p>

3.4.4.9 *Structural Modelling - Static*

Structural geology deals with the study of rock deforming and the structures arising from such a process. Faults, folds and joints are common examples. It also gives basic information about the stress and strain withstood by the rock mass.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Structural Modelling	<p>The current block helps in the forecast of ground instability events through the identification of planes of weakness and possible failure in rock masses. Indeed, the concept of the stability of rock masses and measures to prevent any failures occurring, are linked to the understanding of the structural framework of the rock masses.</p> <p>Dip, dip direction and size of the surfaces are the most critical parameters. Dip and dip direction are expressed in degrees while size is measured in meters of 3D length. This type of data is encountered as 3D triangulated surfaces in various formats. The most usual interchangeable format is *.dxf.</p>

3.4.4.10 *Rock Mass Quality - Static*

The quality assessment of rock mass considers the general condition of the rock mass, including fracture density, weathering and discontinuity. It therefore gives a better view of the general competency of the rock mass in withstanding different forces.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION RMS	<p>The determination of the general stability and integrity of the rock mass is basically accomplished by assessing the quality of the rock mass, which is of prime importance in hazard mapping and risk management. It helps to identify areas of weakness and potential failure, which then allows one to apply specific mitigation to enhance stability within mining operations.</p> <p>The rock mass quality is measured with the usage of different rock classification systems. The output of this process is a unitless number that expresses the quality of the rock mass. The higher the number the better the quality. This kind of data is encountered as polygon vector files or classified raster files that show the spatial extent of the open pit. In 3D environment, the different classes can be described by 3D triangulated bodies in .obj format.</p>

3.4.4.11 *Stratigraphy - Static*

Stratigraphy refers to the study of rock strata and their relationships. It is a peek into the history of geological activity leading to today's ground conditions to enable the understanding of the distribution and characteristics of different rock types.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Stratigraphy	<p>Stratigraphy helps in understanding the different rock types and their distribution and structural properties. This knowledge is imperative for stability analysis, since in it, the interpretation of geological data and the prediction of the ground behaviour in response to various stresses find their context.</p> <p>Like the previous block, this kind of data is encountered as a polygon vector file or a classified raster file that shows the spatial extent of each lithological class at the extent of the open pit. In 3D environment, the different classes can be described by 3D triangulated bodies in .obj format.</p>

3.4.5 Green & Resilience Accountability Component

Description	<p>The Green & Resilience Accountability Component will promote critical raw materials supply chain resilience and sustainability based on the quantification of environmental and socio-economic impact of mining activities for different mining phases (e.g. permission, operation, post-closure).</p> <p>The component will include technological and operational aspects, in addition to environmental and socio-economic features that may enhance end users' resilience and sustainability.</p>
Building blocks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental impact assessment, water, air, soil <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The assessment will be based on integrated satellite data with field data which will be processed. • Socioeconomic metrics <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Collect data on parameters about the population in communities close to mining sites, including access to resources, safe living conditions etc. • Prognostic and dashboard visualizations <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The dashboard will include prognostic features • Resilience index development and implementation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Will include key information about response capabilities to perturbations and shocks. • Sustainability Index VTI development and implementation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Key information to assess environmental performance.

Interfaces

The Green & Resilience Accountability Component will be an integrated framework merging satellite-derived data with on-ground field measurements, in addition to data based on local community socio-cultural characteristics.

Relevant indicators that may contribute to the resilience of the mining sector are e.g. critical infrastructure, workforce, supply chain, and natural resources. The relevance of indicators and the development of a resilience index will be validated through involvement of end-users and experts – Community of Practitioners (CoP). They will provide input on needs, hazards, barriers, local geographical conditions, regulations etc.

TERRAVISION Prognostic and Dashboards Visualizations will involve the development of a modern web tool enabling users to monitor and analyze data generated by the TERRAVISION services. Dashboard Visualizations will incorporate the resilience and sustainability indexes and reflect changes in the mining sector and to provide stakeholders with up-to-date information on the resilience and the sustainability of mining activities.

Figure 22. Functional view of The Green & Resilience Accountability Component

3.4.5.1 *Environmental Impact Assessment (water, air, soil)*

Description

The main objective of this workflow is to monitor and generate indicators of environmental impact on water, air and soil using a combination of satellite imagery, sensor data and raw spectral signatures. The system employs advanced remote sensing techniques and deep learning models to provide accurate and actionable information.

Satellite images, sensor data and spectral signatures are collected, ingested and pre-processed to remove noise, align spatially and temporally, and transform into analysis-ready format and they are stored in TerraFusion Platform.

The system leverages remote sensing techniques, big data processing tools and deep learning models to analyse the data provided in previous steps and generate environmental indicators. Remote sensing techniques are applied to identify specific features:

- Classification of land cover, vegetation, water bodies and pollution by supervised image classification.
- Identification of changes in land use, vegetation and water bodies over time.
- Based on spectral indices computes indices like Normalized Difference Vegetation index (NDVI), Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) () among others.
- Classification and segmentation of surfaces using CNNs.
- Use of Auto encoder networks for feature extraction and dimensionality reduction.
- Analysis of time-series data through Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs).

Finally, satellite data, field data will be integrated with multimodal simulation models to enhance the accuracy of environmental indicators. These models help to predict the future environmental conditions, providing a comprehensive view of potential impacts.

The system continuously monitors data quality and infrastructure health, ensuring reliable operations. The following **environmental indicators** can be computed:

- **Water:** Indicators like turbidity, chlorophyll concentration, and water temperature.
- **Air:** Indicators like particulate matter (PM2.5, PM10), NO2, SO2 levels.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soil: Indicators like soil moisture content, organic matter, contamination levels.
Building blocks	<p>Analysis and Modelling</p> <p>The system leverages big data processing tools and deep learning models to analyse the data.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Remote sensing techniques supervises image classification, change detection, and spectral indices (e.g. NDVI, NDWI) to identify land cover, vegetation, water bodies and pollution. • Use and combination of different deep learning and multi modal models for classification, segmentation, object detection, feature extraction, dimensionality reduction, time-series analysis. <p>Simulation and Integration</p> <p>Building simulation models to predict future environmental conditions and scenarios, providing a comprehensive view of potential impacts.</p> <p>Monitoring</p> <p>Continuous monitoring of data quality and system health ensures reliable operations.</p>
Interfaces	<p>The Environmental Impact Assessment service (EIA) will be a microservices-based architecture deployed using docker. Different containers will communicate via RESTful APIs, allowing for modular development, scaling and maintenance.</p>

3.4.5.2 Analysis and Modelling

The Analysis and Modelling module is a crucial component of the EIA service, utilizing advanced deep learning models, image filtering techniques, and multimodal models to extract meaningful insights from diverse environmental data sources. This module encompasses various sub-modules, each responsible for specific analytical and modelling tasks.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Multimodal Analysis Model	<p>Different techniques will be applied in order to extract environmental key indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CNNs. These models analyse satellite imagery and sensor data to identify and classify features such as land cover types, vegetation health, water bodies and pollution levels.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Autoencoder networks used for feature extraction and dimensionality reduction. • RNNs to process sequential data to identify trends and patterns over time such as changes in air quality or soil moisture levels. <p>Finally, multimodal models will integrate and analyse data from multiple sources such as satellite imagery, sensor data and spectral signatures to combine data and provide a more comprehensive understanding of environmental conditions.</p> <p>Results obtained from this module are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Land cover classification maps • Vegetation Health Indices • Pollution detection and mapping • Time-series analysis and forecasts
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3.4.5.3 *Simulation and Integration*

The Simulation and Integration module is designed to enhance the accuracy and relevance of environmental impact assessments by integrating various data sources and simulating potential future scenarios. This module focuses on combining satellite data with field data, running simulation models, and integrating results from different analytical techniques to provide comprehensive insights.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Simulation environmental model	<p>The main purpose of this module is to build a model which will be able to predict future environmental conditions based on historical and current data through the use of different techniques such as agent-based, dynamic system, statistical and ML predictive models.</p> <p>Data integration will be taking into account to merge data from various sources and having a more comprehensive analysis.</p> <p>By combining simulation techniques with data integration, the Simulation and Integration module provides powerful tools for predicting future environmental conditions, evaluating the impacts of different scenarios, and supporting informed decision-making. This module ensures that the Environmental Impact Assessment service can provide accurate, relevant, and actionable insights for environmental management and policy development.</p>

3.4.5.4 *Monitoring*

The Monitoring module is essential for ensuring the reliability, accuracy, and efficiency of the (EIA) service. This module continuously tracks the system's performance, data quality, and operational health, providing real-time feedback and alerts to maintain optimal functionality.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Environmental Monitoring	<p>The main purpose of this model is to provide information to the dashboard regarding environmental information. Information to provide will be, among other:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weather information: temperature, humidity, precipitation. • Vegetation inventory: coverage area, type of vegetation. • Ground and surface water, soil moisture. • Air quality, greenhouse gas concentrations. • Heap areas monitoring: size, expansion, environmental impact...

3.4.5.5 *Socio-economic metrics*

In addition to technological and operational aspects, the use cases included in the TERRAVISION's platform will comprise environmental and socio-economic features to enhance resilience and sustainability of each demo site. This will support decision making related to sustainable mining practices including the impact of mining operations on local ecosystems.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Socio-economic metrics	<p>A comprehensive set of socio-economic metrics will be developed for the purpose of assessing the environmental impacts of mining activities, along with the development of a dashboard visualization that will include prognostic features.</p> <p>The metrics will capture key aspects of the mining industry, including its economic impact, social impact, and environmental impact.</p>

3.4.5.6 *Prognostic and Dashboards Visualizations*

Description	<p>An application developed with ReactJs displays all useful data or processed data covering project needs.</p> <p>This task involves developing a web tool for monitoring and analysing data from TERRAVISION services through interactive visualizations. The tool will feature a responsive user interface built with HTML5, TypeScript, and Material UI, and employ server-side rendering using</p>
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	<p>React.js for fast loading. Advanced state management with Redux will handle complex UIs, and secure data exchange will be ensured via Rest API with Axios and JSON Web Token (JWT) authentication. Mocking tools like Mock Service Worker (MSW) will facilitate frontend-backend parallel development. Visualization will be enhanced with 3D maps (MapboxGL) and dynamic graphs (ChartJS, Plotly), providing users an interactive data exploration experience, making it a crucial component of the TERRAVISION platform for accessing and visualizing large data volumes.</p>
Building blocks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation and development of mock-up designs' parts • Developing of user-management system • Dummy data providing • Connectivity with Back End and other data-providers
Interfaces	<p>Multiple screens as pages depicting maps, notifications, line charts, bar charts, values on maps etc.</p>

Figure 23. Functional view of TERRAVISION Prognostic and dashboards visualizations

3.4.5.7 *Specification of end-users' and stakeholders' needs*

The application displays different screens for different end-user or stakeholder.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
<p>TERRAVISION</p> <p>Implementation and development of mock-up designs' parts</p>	<p>The first step, "Implementation and development of parts of the mock-up designs," entails creating interactive components for the web tool. This begins with a detailed analysis of the provided mock-ups to comprehend the intended layout, design elements, and user interactions. Following this, the development environment is set up with essential tools and technologies, including HTML5, TypeScript, Material UI, React.js, and Redux. The basic structure of the application is then developed, which includes the main layout, navigation, and placeholders for various components.</p> <p>A key part of this step involves developing map components by integrating MapboxGL to enable 3D accelerated maps and customizing them with layers, markers, tooltips, and controls for zooming and panning. Dynamic data handling is also implemented to ensure maps can be updated based on user interactions. Additionally, other visualization components are developed using ChartJS and Plotly libraries to create interactive charts and graphs, along with interactive elements like hover effects and clickable regions. State management is set up with Redux to handle the application's state and ensure smooth interaction and data flow between components, while asynchronous actions and API calls are managed using Redux middleware. Backend communication is facilitated by developing a mock API with tools like MSW, allowing frontend development to proceed independently, and Axios is configured for making secure API requests with JWT authentication.</p>

3.4.5.8 *Developing of user-management system*

Developing a user-management system involves creating a software application for managing user accounts and permissions within a platform. The process includes requirement analysis to gather system needs, design of system architecture and interfaces, implementation of backend and frontend components, and integration of authentication mechanisms. It also involves testing to ensure functionality, security, and user acceptance. After deployment, the system requires ongoing maintenance and updates. Key features include user registration, role-based access control, password management, and audit logging.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
<p>TERRAVISION</p>	<p>The user login management system will be built around user's registration and authentication processes, leveraging the identified user roles and permissions to manage access levels. For user</p>

Developing of user-management system	<p>registration, APIs will be created to handle the sign-up process, ensuring input data is thoroughly validated for correct email formats and strong passwords. Authentication mechanisms will be developed using JWT to securely manage user sessions, providing a reliable method for users to log in and maintain their authenticated state. Password management features, including password reset and recovery via email, will also be implemented to ensure users can securely regain access to their accounts if needed.</p> <p>On the front end, user-friendly registration and login forms will be designed using React.js and Material UI, focusing on a seamless and intuitive user experience. These forms will allow new users to sign up and existing users to log in with ease. Additionally, profile management interfaces will be developed, enabling users to view and update their profile information, ensuring they can keep their data current and secure. This comprehensive approach to user login management will ensure a smooth and secure experience for all users, from regular users to administrators.</p>
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3.4.5.9 *Dummy Data providing*

Dummy data provision involves generating and using artificial data to simulate real user information during the development and testing phases of a software application. This practice helps in testing functionality, performance, and security without compromising actual user data.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Dummy Data providing	<p>To provide dummy data for web development, start by identifying data requirements: determine the data structure you need, such as user profiles, product details, or posts, and list the fields and their data types (e.g., name (string), age (integer), email (string)). Then, generate dummy data using automated tools and libraries designed for this purpose. Finally, integrate the dummy data into your project by storing it in static files (e.g., JSON, CSV) and loading these files into your application.</p>

3.4.5.10 *Connectivity with Back End and other data-providers*

Connectivity with the back end and other data providers involves establishing a reliable and secure communication link between the front-end application and the back-end servers or external data sources to exchange and synchronize data efficiently.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Connectivity with Back End and other data-providers	To ensure seamless communication between the client and server, REST API technology will be integrated with the use of the Axios library alongside JWT authentication, providing a safe data exchange while enhancing the overall user experience. Axios simplifies HTTP requests, enabling easy handling of API calls, while JWT ensures secure and stateless authentication, protecting user data during transmission. To facilitate rapid prototyping of the API and allow for the parallel development of the frontend. This approach enables us to simulate real API interactions and continue building features without waiting for the backend to be fully implemented, thus streamlining the development process.

3.4.5.11 *Resilience Index Development and Implementation*

Resilience perspective represent a proactive management approach and principles for handling both normal operations, expected and unexpected events to minimize the impact of any natural hazard event on human or build environments, in addition to facilitate the ability of local communities to be prepared and to handle these conditions.

The resilience index will allow efficient reporting of industry actors with respect to operational conditions. The resilience index framework considers mines as critical infrastructures. The resilience index within the context of the TERRAVISION project represents a pioneering effort in the mining industry to enhance its ability to cope with expected/ unexpected disruptions and challenges.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION Resilience index	<p>The resilience index will be developed for the purpose of providing key information about response capabilities to perturbations and shocks. Relevant factors and indicators contributing to the resilience of the mining sector are e.g. infrastructure, workforce, supply chain, and natural resources.</p> <p>An integrated framework of satellite-derived data, on-ground field measurements, and socio-cultural data, offers an assessment of the mining sector's resilience ability to handle normal variations, changes and disruptions.</p> <p>Indicators and an index will be designed to provide a comprehensive assessment of the sector's overall performance and to identify areas for improvement.</p>

3.4.5.12 Sustainability Index (SI) VTI Development and Implementation

Description	To support the mining industry with their reporting obligations on sustainability, a SI for the mining cycle will be developed and implemented. The developed index will be tested by the companies to check the usability. The innovative part of this index consists of the combination of company data with EO services data.
Building blocks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Map existing SIs, focus on those used by mining companies. • Map EO data available (T 11.1) • Map reporting obligations as included in the Corporate Sustainability Reporting (CSR) directive. • Develop a SI framework. • Calculate and assess the TERRAVISION SI. • Implement the TERRAVISION SI by incorporating it into the TERRAVISION dashboard
Interfaces	A sustainability dashboard showing how sustainable the company is overall, as well as a breakdown of the contributing factors and indicators.

3.4.5.13 Map SIs

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
Map SI	The strengths and weaknesses of existing SI used will be evaluated. Also, the viability of a generic index which can be applied by different mining companies around EU will be assessed. The evaluation will cover both the assessment criteria as well as the calculation methods used, with a special focus on economic, social, technical and environmental factors considered.

3.4.5.14 Map EO data

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
Map EO data	<p>Review and evaluate the data obtained by means of EO services in the previous tasks of TERRAVISION.</p> <p>Select EO data which fit with the data needed for the SI (economic, social, technical, and environmental factors) and evaluate if these data could improve the quality of the index and solve data-gaps.</p>

3.4.5.15 *Map reporting obligation CSRD*

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
Map CSRD reporting obligations	Reporting obligations of the CSR-Directive will be analysed. These obligations will be compared to the SI evaluated. This analysis will have a special focus on economic, social, technical and environmental factors to be able to align these obligations as well as possible to the SI that will be developed.

3.4.5.16 *Develop a SI framework*

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
Develop a SI framework	<p>A state-of-the-art SI framework will be developed considering existing SI and CSRD reporting obligations. The framework will make use of EO services as developed in the TERRAVISION project, in combination with company data available. The index will score the overall sustainability of the company, as well as a breakdown of the contributing factors and indicators. This will be done in a similar way as done or used by other indices or classification methods, such as the United Nations Framework Classification (UNFC) methodology. The UNFC methodology defines the maturity of a wide range of projects to support the sustainable development of energy and mineral resources, including anthropogenic resources. The result of the SI framework will comply to the CSRD reporting standards.</p> <p>The index will make use of information gathered for the environmental impact assessment (T11.1) and socio-economic metrics (T11.2). A good alignment of the information needs for this task (T11.4) with T11.1 and T11.2 is therefore of high importance.</p> <p>The index developed should allow to be regularly updated to reflect changes in the mining company in near real-time to be able to provide stakeholders with up-to-date information on the sustainability of mining activities.</p>

3.4.5.17 Calculate the TERRAVISION SI

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
Calculate the TERRAVISION SI	<p>The SI will be calculated for the mining companies that are part of the TERRAVISION project using the framework and data available.</p> <p>The robustness of the TERRAVISION SI will be assessed based on the calculations made for the mining companies that are part of the TERRAVISION consortium. This will be done by thoroughly analysing the results and perform sensitivity and uncertainty analysis.</p>

3.4.5.18 Implement the TERRAVISION SI

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
Implement the TERRAVISION SI	<p>The SI will be implemented by incorporating it into the TERRAVISION dashboard, including the development of attractive visualisations of the results, which is part of T11.3. therefore a good alignment between both tasks is needed. The dashboard should include up-to-date information to allow the mining companies to follow up their activities with near real-time information.</p>

4. Information view

The diagram in Figure 27 sets out a comprehensive workflow for integrating diverse datasets and processing them into actionable insights for mineral exploration. The process commences with the acquisition of data from a variety of sources, including EO satellite, airborne and ground-based in situ sensors. CDSE supplies EO data, while OpenEO is used for data discovery, access, and management. Third-party providers such as EnMap, PRISMA, HR and VHR EO services (e.g., Airbus, Maxar) provide additional satellite data, further enhancing the data pool. The dataset is further improved by the incorporation of other data, such as weather records, airborne data, and in situ spectral sensors.

Field samples collected during exploration are analysed in laboratories and, once processed, the data is stored in the TerraFusion platform. This storage allows field-derived information to be seamlessly integrated into exploration workflows alongside other data sources.

Once the data has been collected, it is transformed into a common format through the harmonisation process. This ensures the accuracy and consistency of data from a wide variety of sources. It is essential that data is harmonised to facilitate seamless integration and maintain data quality.

After harmonisation, the data is separated into two back ends:

- EO data is managed in the TerraFusion platform, which handles discovery, access, processing and storage.
- Non-spaceborne and other non-satellite data is stored in the Non-spaceborne Data Backend.

Once the data has been stored, the pre-processing phase begins, during which the data is transformed into ARD. This step allows the data to be presented in a standardised, usable format for subsequent analysis. Once the pre-processing phase is complete, SR modelling is applied to the EO data enhancing the spatial resolution.

Next, advanced ML models are developed at both pixel and feature levels, performing data fusion by integrating spaceborne, airborne, and ground-based datasets. The multi-source fusion process improves the overall accuracy and comprehensiveness of the exploration process. The data fusion outputs feed into the TerraFusion Platform, the Non-Spaceborne Data Backend, and into the CoreSmart predictor, an Artificial Intelligence (AI)-driven tool designed to predict mineral presence and grades. This prediction is supported by a spectral knowledge library, which consolidates spectral signatures derived from hyperspectral data, field samples, and drill core samples. The library is critical for the automation of mineral identification, providing spectral matching and analysis to validate exploration results. To verify the accuracy of remote sensing predictions, field validation through laboratory analyses and in situ sampling is conducted.

Once the data is in a usable form, it is analysed and processed to support the creation of various EO mining services. These services are divided across three platforms: CDSE, GEP, and the TerraFusion. On the CDSE side, deployed services include the RM exploration, the EO-based monitoring of stockpile volumes and extraction rates, and the generation of primary and secondary RM maps. The TerraFusion platform will host five key services: dynamic hazard

mapping, resilience and sustainability indices, CoreSmart predictor advancements, and a processability indicator. The surface deformation mapping will be deployed via the GEP platform.

These services address various stages of the mining life cycle, contributing to efficient, sustainable, and resilient mining operations. The final deployment phase ensures that these tools and services are accessible to end users, such as mining operators and decision-makers, who can apply data-driven insights to real-world mining operations.

Figure 24. The diagram of the information flow

5. Deployment & Operation View

The TERRAVISION services will be deployed in cloud-native environments using containerization technologies. This will enable them to run on any infrastructure, from private clouds to public cloud providers. This strategy fits the microservices architecture as all components in the architecture consist of various building blocks, communicating with each other. By breaking down applications into smaller services, better development and deployment strategies can be utilized, leading also to better use of cloud-native environments.

To manage and orchestrate these containerized services effectively Kubernetes will be used. Kubernetes provides a powerful platform for automating the deployment, scaling, and operations of containers. The self-healing feature automatically restarts failed containers, reschedules containers when nodes die, and kills unresponsive containers. Additionally, Kubernetes supports rolling updates and rollbacks, enabling us to deploy updates to applications without downtime and revert if issues are detected.

Regular backups of critical data and configurations will be performed to ensure data recovery in the event of a failure. Backups will be scheduled to capture data at frequent intervals, minimizing potential data loss.

6. Architectural Perspectives

6.1 Security and Privacy Perspective

All platform APIs will be developed and maintained in compliance with industry security standards and best practices. The data that is handled by TERRAVISION components will be protected against unauthorized access and potential threats.

TERRAVISION will use secure authentication protocols to verify the identity of users and systems interacting with the APIs. OAuth 2.0 and OpenID Connect standards will be implemented, providing a reliable framework for authentication, while various authentication flows can be used that are suitable for the different client types. All API requests by any client service will require an access token obtained through a secure authentication process. Users will authenticate using their credentials, and upon successful verification, they will receive an access token that must be included in the header of all subsequent API requests. This token-based authentication ensures that only authenticated users and services can access the API endpoints.

TERRAVISION will also use authorization controls to manage access to resources for both users and services. Access rights will be determined based on roles and permissions assigned to users and services. Users and services will be granted only the minimum level of access necessary to perform their functions, minimizing potential security risks. Each role will have specific permissions about what operations can be performed. When an API request is received, the system will check the user's or service's permissions against the requested resource and block any unauthorized requests.

6.2 Performance & Scalability Perspective

Ensuring performance and scalability is important to TERRAVISION platform's ability to deliver reliable services. The architecture should handle varying workloads and maintain a high performance.

By deploying services within containers managed by Kubernetes, as is already mentioned scalability can be achieved. Kubernetes supports the automatic scaling of resources based on real-time demand, enabling the platform to handle spikes in usage. The modular architecture of TERRAVISION Platform, consisting of building blocks that are independent, enables components to be scaled based on their individual performance requirements.

Furthermore, continuous monitoring is essential for improving performance. Tools for metrics collection will be used, providing real-time insights into the system's performance. This includes application performance monitoring tools to track request latencies, error rates, and throughput, as well as infrastructure monitoring to track resource utilization and system health. Also, by collecting log data, the system's behaviour can be analysed to identify issues and ensure the reliability of services. This information is essential for maintaining system health, performance and security, while also ensuring scalability.

7. UX design and user feedback

<p>Description</p>	<p>Creating a web development tool that aligns with end-users' needs, providing prognostic features for the mining industry.</p> <p>During the UX design and user feedback phase, CORE's focus will be on designing a web development tool that aligns with end-users' needs, providing prognostic features for the mining industries involved (TERNAMAG, CANTERAS, THARSIS). Utilizing tools such as Figma and React, CORE IC's team will visualize the User Interface (UI) with mock-ups and wireframes, illustrating user paths to key actions. The goal is to discern web developers' requirements and expectations, establishing necessary use cases and data flows to support the tool's technical components. CORE will use a co-creation approach, engaging with both end users and external stakeholders to define pilot scenarios and consolidate user needs. This process involves dynamic, adaptable, and collaborative approaches to translate user needs into structured system requirements. The team will develop a comprehensive map of end-user requirements, use cases and datasets, leading to the finalization of the system architecture tailored to end-user needs and supporting technical components. This phase is crucial for ensuring the tool is user-friendly and meets web developers' expectations.</p>
<p>Building blocks</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requirements Collecting end-users' requirements • Specifications Collecting end-users' and stakeholders' specifications • UX Design Creating UI mock-ups and wireframes of use cases' (Figma, React.js) • Feedback Consolidating feedback from end-users' to System Architecture
<p>Interfaces</p>	<p>The UX design for the TERRAVISION platform will serve as an initial concept, illustrating how the platform will appear and function. This design will encompass both the technical and functional components of the project, ensuring that all necessary data is gathered and integrated effectively. Following this, the design will undergo a feedback phase where user and stakeholder input will be collected. This feedback will inform the validation process, leading to iterative improvements and refinements. The outcome of this component will aim ultimately to culminate in the UX/UI development of the TERRAVISION Platform.</p>

Figure 25. Functional view of TERRAVISION UX Design and User Feedback

7.1 Requirements

The project should ensure compatibility with existing systems and standards, facilitating seamless integration and data exchange across different platforms and technologies. Each use case of the TERRAVISION project will provide its specific requirements to ensure a comprehensive understanding and alignment with the overarching objective.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION End-users' Requirements	<p>Focusing on use cases, a detailed set of user requirements will be developed and configured for each use case. The activity will consider both functional and non-functional requirements and constraints.</p> <p>Collecting user requirements is crucial for the development of the TERRAVISION platform because they ensure that the platform provides the necessary information. These requirements will define the values, metrics, indications and graphics that need to be presented, guiding how these elements will be depicted in the UX design to meet user needs effectively.</p>

7.2 Specifications

Technical Specifications refer to a detailed, precise description of the technical requirements, standards, and criteria that the platform must meet. This encompasses the system architecture, outlining the overall structure and design, as well as functional requirements specifying the system's features and capabilities. Performance criteria are established to ensure speed, reliability, capacity, and scalability. Interoperability standards are set to guarantee compatibility and seamless integration with other systems. UI and experience requirements ensure the system is user-friendly and accessible. Security measures are detailed to protect against threats, including encryption, authentication, and access control. Compliance with industry standards, regulations, and best practices is mandatory.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION End-users' and stakeholders' Specifications	Focusing on use cases, a detailed set of user specifications will be developed and configured for each use case. System specifications are vital for outlining the functional requirements by listing essential properties that must be implemented to develop end-user and use-case-driven EO mining services. Additionally, they address non-functional requirements such as performance, scalability, security, and privacy, which are crucial for the system's overall effectiveness and reliability. By defining the TERRAVISION reference architecture in terms of the system, the specifications provide a high-level view of layers, components, tools, and applications, ensuring a cohesive interaction pattern, technical integration points, interconnection schemes, and specific interfaces for information exchange, including with the CDSE initiative. This comprehensive system-level specification allows for a clear mapping of basic functionalities. By implementing these specifications into the TERRAVISION platform, we ensure that each use case and collaborating stakeholders will meet their needs, providing tailored solutions that address the unique requirements and challenges of each specific application.

7.3 UX Design

UX design refers to the process of creating and optimizing a product or system to enhance the overall experience of its users. This design discipline focuses on understanding user needs, behaviours, and challenges to ensure that interactions with the product are intuitive, efficient, and satisfying. UX design encompasses a range of activities, including user research, wireframing, prototyping, usability testing, and refining interfaces. The goal is to create solutions that are not only functional but also user-friendly, engaging and accessible, thereby improving user satisfaction and ensuring that the product effectively meets its intended purpose.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION UX Design	After gaining the requirements and specifications from the end-users, the technical team from CORE can begin creating the platform, using these requirements and specifications as their guidelines. With a clear understanding of how each use case envisions the design, the team will follow a consistent UX design approach, while accommodating the unique diversities of each mine. Utilizing Figma and React.js as their primary tools, the Front-End team will focus on delivering a practical, user-friendly interface that clearly depicts all essential information. The final design will prominently feature TERRAVISION Innovation Services, ensuring a cohesive and intuitive user experience across the platform.

7.4 Feedback

Gaining feedback in a group project is crucial because it ensures that all members' perspectives and needs are considered, fostering a collaborative environment where ideas can be refined and improved. This iterative process helps align the project with its goals, ultimately leading to a system architecture unified for all end users and stakeholders that meets the collective requirements and expectations.

Building Block Name	Building Block Description
TERRAVISION UX Design's Feedback	Feedback from end users and stakeholders is crucial to ensure that the UX design meets their needs and adheres to their requirements. This iterative feedback process allows the technical team to validate that the design effectively supports all technical components and functionalities envisioned for the platform. By actively incorporating user and stakeholder input, the team can identify and address any gaps or areas for improvement, ensuring a more user-centric and functional design. Feedback will be received through meetings and emails, maintaining continuous contact with the pilots and other involved companies throughout the entire UX design process. This ongoing communication is essential for a smooth and efficient procedure, helping to ensure that the final system architecture is optimized for everyone. After gathering and analysing the feedback, necessary amendments will be made to the platform, refining and enhancing its features to better align with user expectations and project goals, ultimately leading to a mutually accepted Architecture that will be adopted by TERRAVISION platform.

8. Conclusion

The development of the high-level architecture has established a framework within which the various building blocks can be developed and combined to successfully create the TERRAVISION platform. It provides a comprehensive overview of the TERRAVISION system, outlining the main components, their interactions, and supporting the development of end-user and use case-driven EO mining services. The document provides guidance for the implementation and integration of the system components, ensuring that they are aligned with the project objectives. In addition, the architectural diagram and detailed descriptions (including diagrams and figures) of the structural elements provide a solid foundation for the subsequent phases of the project, ensuring a smooth transition and avoiding unnecessary complications. The process of collecting inputs was carried out through continuous communication and discussions with the task leaders, including examination, review, and sending feedback for modifications and omissions. Additionally, the responsible for each task provided valuable insights and recommendations. The comprehensive breakdown of the building blocks also identified initial architectural gaps, which were subsequently addressed to enhance the overall design. This bidirectional approach ensured that the architecture is robust and aligned with the project requirements identified in tasks 4.1 and 4.2. The architecture was designed in such a way as to allow further efforts to improve and implement new proposals. This dynamic way ensures that the TERRAVISION platform develops effectively, and in a way that meets the changing needs of users and stakeholders. The results of this work will support the creation of a robust, user-focused EO mining service that is well-equipped for real-world applications.

9. References

Ogush, M. A., Coleman, D., & Beringer, D. (2000). *A template for documenting software and firmware architectures* (Version 1.3, 15-Mar-00). Hewlett-Packard Product Generation Solutions.

Woods, E. (2005) *Software Architecture Using ViewPoints and Perspectives*. Zurich: SET2005.